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D2.1 Use case scenarios definition and design

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D2.1 – Use Case Scenarios Definition and Design

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BMC	Business Model Canvas
BWC	Burgas Water Company
DL	Deep Learning
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
HPC	High Performance Computing
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Lifecycle Assessment
ML	Machine Learning
NLP	Natural Language Processing
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
WP	Work Package
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence

Executive summary

This document (D2.1 “Use case scenarios definition and design”) was developed within the framework of WP2 “Specifications and Co-Creation for AI-Based Policy Management”. WP2 is devoted to producing key specifications for the project’s AI-based policy making paradigm, while including the user studies and the co-creation activities.

This deliverable contains a definition of the pilots, a characterization of Use Cases and a list of User Stories. The user stories described in this document will be used by the technical Work Packages in order to drive the technical work they will develop, therefore, the user stories described here will be the basis of this work.

In this project, we have 5 pilots and a total of 16 Use Cases:

- The Athens Pilot focuses on citizen-centric management and optimization of city resources and has 3 use cases, which are, Maintenance policies optimization, Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development and Economic/Revenue Policies Modelling.
- The Genoa Pilot focuses on evidence based policies for optimizing resources used to offer support and assistance services for the citizens of the Genova and has also 3 use cases, which are, Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people, Optimizing the Allocation and Use of Resources for Social and Demographic Services also via fostering the interoperability between information systems and More effective extraordinary maintenance interventions by enhancing the “SegnalaCI” Citizens’ Suggestions/Reports and Policies Visualizations.
- The Nicosia Pilot focuses on provide data-driven evidence-based policies for optimizing mobility in Nicosia, based on Effective Policies for Holistic Mobility and Accessibility and has 3 uses cases, which are, Optimal Urban mobility policies for citizens, Optimal Urban mobility policies for the Municipality and Accessible urban mobility policies.
- The Lisbon Pilot focuses on gathering relevant and valid data sources, such as weather, buildings’ characteristics, and energy consumption, and with the aid of AI and machine learning algorithms detect patterns and problems regarding energy efficiency, so that possible data-driven policies can be defined to ensure a more sustainable and efficient environment in the city and has 5 uses cases, which are, Renewables (PV) potential and performance analysis, Buildings Energy Performance Analysis, Budget Planning for Energy Usage and Buildings Renovation, City’s thermal and air quality performance, and City’s greenhouse gases emissions.
- And the Burgas Pilot focuses on develop a data-driven policy making tool for the maintenance of the water management infrastructure through data gathered from the infrastructure itself via fiber optic devices installed with no dig techniques and has 2 uses cases, which are, Smart Water Management System - Pobeda Residential Neighbourhood and Condition-based Monitoring and LCA for Maintenance and Repair Policies.

To identify and characterize the User Stories from all AI4PublicPolicy stakeholders, we followed a methodology based on the Business Model Canvas to collect information about the pilots, use cases and user stories. The User Stories described in this document will be used in other AI4PP activities, such as co-creation workshops that use them as a baseline for their discussions and thereby update and improve user stories. Another example of the use of User Stories is that Technical WPs use user stories to identify scenarios of use of the technology being developed in the context of the project.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI's potential for automated, transparent, and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e. AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens' participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organization transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project's AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project's developments. AI4PublicPolicy's business plan for sustaining, expanding, and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project's platform.

1.2 Description of WP2

The main objectives of WP2 are to:

- Specify the overall architecture for the AI4PublicPolicy platform by identifying components, their functionalities and interconnection, ensuring their coherency with the requirements and global architecture.
- Identify and track end user and technical requirements provided by the use case partners and the technical contributors of AI4PublicPolicy.
- Review the standards and regulations and identify appropriate ones that need to be monitored and followed in the project.
- Analyse the policy making processes to ensure that the outcomes of the project address and enhance/improve these processes, while reducing the bottlenecks in public administration and ensuring high quality and adoption of results.
- Define the data models of the datasets to be utilized for the development, training and actual utilization of the AI models and algorithms of AI4PublicPolicy.
- Define the co-creation. Relevant activities will be regularly reported in D2.8, in-line with the description of the deliverable.

1.3 Purpose and scope

This deliverable is the result of the work of *Task 2.1 - Reference Scenarios and Use Cases* that started in month 1 ends in month 6 and is part of WP2, which includes tasks 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4 2.5 and 2.6. The purpose of the task is "*elicited, collect, and analyse Pilots, Use Cases and User Stories regarding safe, secure, and citizen-centered AI in policy development environments. User Stories from different stakeholders will be considered, including policy makers and local actors. Within this task the analysis and definition of the use cases will be conducted in order to identify these User Stories, which will be checked against the offerings of the AI4PublicPolicy technologies as well as their generic applicability, and reusability to different scenarios. This will be the basis for the use cases implementation and experimentation.*".

The main focus of this document is to create a list of User Stories, which will be fundamental to the technical Work Packages that will be used as inputs of the technical work. To create the User Stories list, it was necessary to define the pilots participating in the project and characterize the Use Cases. The User Stories list will be used as the basic principles of the project and all other tasks and work packages will be taken into account when preparing all project developments, making this list a fundamental working tool.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

D2.1 “Use case scenarios definition and design” involves five chapters that discuss and analyse in detail different thematic topics concerning the outline the design of the scenarios, including their initial mapping to AI4PublicPolicy outcomes and cloud-based services.

More specifically:

- The **first chapter** of the document is introductory, aiming to provide some basic information regarding the AI4PublicPolicy project, a brief description of WP2 “Specifications and Co-Creation for AI-Based Policy Management”, the purpose and scope of the deliverable, its structure and relation to other WPs and tasks.
- The **second chapter** of the deliverable provides a view on the approach used by the AI4PublicPolicy, on how to collect information about the Use Case and the User Stories.
- The **third chapter** of the document describes a list of Pilots and Use Cases provided by AI4PublicPolicy pilots.
- The **fourth chapter** provides a list of Ai4PP User Stories.

Finally, the document includes a **fifth chapter** with the conclusions of the document, as well as a section with useful **appendices** related to the document.

1.5 Relation to other WPs and tasks

WP2 “Specifications and co-creation for AI-based policy management” is devoted to producing key specifications for the project’s AI-based policy making paradigm, while including the user studies and the co-creation activities, as you can see in image below(Figure 1). More specifically, this work package:

- interacts horizontally with WP1 that includes all the project management activities of AI4PublicPolicy and monitors all the work packages.
- drives all the technical development work packages of the project (i.e., WP3, WP4, WP5, WP7) through providing technical specifications and the AI4PublicPolicy platform architecture.
- has a two-way interaction with the pilot tasks of WP6; on the one hand, the WP2 user studies and co-creation session will provide requirements for integrating and operating the pilot systems, while at the same time receiving feedback from the pilot systems regarding the specifications of the AI technologies and VPME of the project.
- feeds WP8 with useful content to disseminate regarding the advances of the pilots and the outcomes of the co-creation activities of the project.

Hence, WP2 interacts with all the other WPs of the project by providing specifications, requirements, and feedback on both a technical and implementational level.

Figure 1: AI4PublicPolicy project workplan

With respect to this document (Deliverable D2.1), its focus is on the collection of User Stories, which will form the basis of the work of the AI4PublicPolicy project. The User Stories described in this document will be used in other WP2 activities, such as co-creation workshops that use them as a baseline for their discussions and thereby update and improve user stories, and by the technical team handling the definition of the AI4PP platform architecture. The technical WPs (WP3, WP4 and WP5) will also use the here defined User Stories, to establish scenarios for the use of the technologies being developed within the context of the technical WPs.

2 Methodology

To identify and characterize the User Stories from all AI4PublicPolicy stakeholders, we followed a well-defined methodology. This methodology was based on the Business Model Canvas (BMC)¹, which is one of the most widely used models for the definition of Business Models. For this task, we used only a sub-set of the Business model canvas, dedicated to the Value Proposition. Figure 2 shows this Value proposition canvas. The Value Proposition Canvas Methodology has the purpose to collect information and in a very simple way identify the User of the story, the reason behind the story (pain or gain), and its objective.

Figure 2: Value Proposition Canvas Methodology

This Methodology has the purpose to help AI4PublicPolicy Stakeholders identify their objectives and the reasons behind these objectives, and how these can be achieved. The structure of the methodology provides a visual advantage by facilitating the association of the value propositions with the stakeholders' requirements.

2.1 Approach

Based on the Value Proposition Canvas methodology, a questionnaire (detailed in Appendix 1) was created to collect information from all the AI4PublicPolicy stakeholders.

Figure 3: Approach for User Story collection

¹ Osterwalder A. P., 2015 - Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2013

The questionnaire asks for a summary of the pilot and an extended description, the motivation and drivers, and some detail of the Place - location and characterization, and the entity type, (e.g. type of organisation).

The Use Case should have, like the pilot, a summary and a detailed description, value proposition with examples and its documentation related to the Use Case, if applicable.

The User Stories must be short, simple descriptions of a feature told from the perspective of the person who desires the new capability, usually a user or customer of the system. A User Story should be comprised of 3 main parts:

- 1) Type of User: Identifies the customer job(s) to which this user story relates.
- 2) Some Goal: Describes the intended goal that the user expects to be fulfilled.
- 3) Some Reason: Identifies the reason(s) to which this user story relates.

The User Stories described in this document are used as a baseline in the co-creation workshops, which will make them improved and updated. These User Stories have already been discussed in a co-creation workshop, but there will be more workshops in the future, which will lead to a continuing process of updating and improving the User Stories, including input from the technical WPs.

3 Pilots and Use Cases

In AI4PP, we have in total of 5 pilots, that are spread across Europe. The map below represents the 5 pilots of the project, which are developed and deployed in the following European cities:

1. Athens;
2. Genoa;
3. Nicosia;
4. Lisbon;
5. Burgas.

Figure 4: Map with the 5 Pilots

3.1 Use Cases Overview

The chart below, provides an overview of the Use Cases per Pilot. The Lisbon Pilot has the most use Cases, in total 5, Athens, Genoa, and Nicosia Pilots each with 3 and the Burgas Pilot, has 2 Use Cases. The complete list of Use Cases for each pilot is attached (Appendix 2 – Complete List of Use Case).

Figure 5: Number of Use Case per Pilot

The following table provides an overview of the project's pilots, including their categories and their Use Cases.

Table 1: Pilot Leaders and Policies Involved

Pilot Location	Pilot Leaders	Category – Policies Involved	Use Cases
Athens - Greece	DAEM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies for Infrastructures Maintenance and Repair • Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use Case #1: Maintenance policies optimization • Use Case #2: Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development • Use Case #3: Economic/Revenue Policies Modelling
Genoa - Italy	CDG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies for Citizens and Business Services Optimization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use Case #1: Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people • Use Case #2: Optimizing the Allocation and Use of Resources for Social and Demographic Services also via fostering the interoperability between information systems • Use Case #3: More effective extraordinary maintenance interventions by enhancing the “SegnalaCI” Citizens’ Suggestions/Reports and Policies Visualizations
Nicosia - Cyprus	NIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies for Holistic Urban Mobility and Accessibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use Case #1: Optimal Urban mobility policies for citizens • Use Case #2: Optimal Urban mobility policies for the Municipality • Use Case #3: Accessible urban mobility policies
Lisbon - Portugal	LIS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Management and Optimization Policies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use Case #1: Renewables (PV) potential and performance analysis • Use Case #2: Buildings Energy Performance Analysis • Use Case #3: Budget Planning for Energy Usage and Buildings Renovation • Use Case #4: City’s thermal and air quality performance • Use Case #5: City’s greenhouse gases emissions
Burgas - Bulgaria	BUR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use Case #1: Smart Water Management System - Pobeda Residential Neighbourhood

		Maintenance Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use Case #2: Condition-based Monitoring and LCA for Maintenance and Repair Policies
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3.2 Pilot #1 – Athens – Greece

Pilot	
Pilot Name	Citizen Centric Management and Optimization of City Resources
Summary	The pilot aims at developing, demonstrating, and evaluating data-driven, citizen-centric and evidence-based policies about the maintenance of the city’s infrastructure and the citizens’ transport and urban mobility, including the economic implications of these policies.
Description	<p>The pilot aims at developing, demonstrating, and evaluating data-driven, citizen-centric and evidence-based policies about the maintenance of the city’s infrastructure and the citizens’ transport and urban mobility, including the economic implications of these policies. To this end, the pilot will leverage readily available datasets of the city including information about vehicles parking and mobility, the database of fines, information about the maintenance resources (e.g., maintenance workers) of the city, as well as economic information (e.g., fees paid by citizens and business in different areas). However, the pilot will also take advantage of large amounts of crowdsourced data from the city’s suite of citizen engagement tools that are provided and deployed by partner NOVO (i.e., the Novoville Platform and Apps). The latter tools facilitate real-time interactions (transactions, requests, communication) between citizens and the city’s services. They comprise three primary vertical applications, including: (i) Incident/problem reporting; (ii) A Smart Parking solution that integrates real-time information from on-street parking sensors, and helps motorists locate an available parking space; (iii) Citizens’ opinion mining and public consultation and communication tools, which enable the collection and reception of feedback on policy and planning actions. These vertical applications provide a wealth of citizen-centric data, that can be combined with the city’s databases in order to extract evidence-based policies in the target areas. The pilot will involve the creation of a dedicated instance of the project’s VPME, which will integrate anonymized data streams from the above listed sources and will enable DAEM to extract, benchmark, simulate and validate evidence-based policies. DAEM will access the VPME instance and the project’s AI tools in order to extract recommendations for maintenance and transport policies, including their economic implications. In this direction, the VPME will enable DAEM to execute and visualize AI-based analytics (ML/DL/RL) on the above city-related data sources through single interface. In parallel, DAEM will be also able to use the existing digital public interfaces (mobile/web apps), in order to provide policy-related feedback to citizens and to create open feedback loops as part of continuous and frequent interactions between the city and the citizens. In this way, the AI4PublicPolicy VPME and its tools will improve the transparency and acceptability of the policy development process, the planning of policies, the accountability of the city, as well as the overall trust on the resulting policies.</p>
Motivation	The city of Athens is the capital city and largest Municipality in Greece. It serves a population of about 750,000 people, swelling to almost 3 million when daily commuters are included. Athens is one of the most popular tourist destinations in Europe, welcoming more than 5.5 million visitors per year. Athens was named European Capital of Innovation for 2018. The city has a

	<p>complex and aged infrastructure (roads, water pipelines, streetlights, public spaces, public buildings, garbage collection facilities, etc.). Maintaining basic city infrastructure and public facilities in working order is therefore a tedious and resource-demanding task. This, combined with complex workflows and organizational procedures, makes the task even harder. Furthermore, as the heart of one of Europe's largest metropolitan areas, Athens must deal with significant traffic flows in the city, which must be handled in cost effective and environment efficient ways, but also in ways acceptable by the citizens. In response to these challenges, the city aspires to develop reusable, evidence based and citizen-centric models and policies, which will enable the public authority to optimize the efficiency of its infrastructure maintenance and transport management activities, in ways that are acceptable by the citizens. To develop such models and policies, the city can take advantage of large volumes of data that it collects from a variety of data sources, including crowdsourced data gathered from the citizens, transportation data collected from city sensors (e.g., parking) and citizens' reports, as well as data available in the municipality's databases. The analysis of these data can be hardly performed by humans alone without proper IT-based tools. AI technologies and tools could significantly boost the automation and efficiency of extracting policies from the available data, as a means of producing optimal policies regarding decision making and resources allocation for maintaining the city infrastructure, as well as regarding optimal urban mobility. Likewise, XAI can boost the transparency of the policy development process, while existing public digital interfaces for citizens' interactions (e.g., city apps) can boost the continuous engagement of citizens in the policy development process towards an acceptable, trustworthy and citizen centric outcome.</p>
	<p>Place(s)</p>
<p>Place Name</p>	<p>City of Athens, Greece</p>
<p>Place Location</p>	<p>Greece, Attica Region, City of Athens</p>
<p>Characterisation</p>	<p>At the moment there are two mobile applications operating for the City of Athens relevant to the Pilots, one for Citizen Engagement and one for parking space management. More specifically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The Citizen Engagement Platform (provided by Novoville) enables citizens to: ● Report issues that come across in their city and get real time updates on the repair status ● Quickly find and navigate to points-of-interest on the city map ● Get notified about emergencies, important announcements and events that are happening around them. <p>myAthensPass is a mobile app that revolutionises the way drivers pay for parking spaces in controlled zones within the City of Athens, improving the quality of life in the city. The application allows drivers to pay for parking straight from their mobile device, quickly, easily, and conveniently.</p> <p>With myAthensPass the drivers can:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Find their exact location via GPS ● Select the parking duration they want

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purchase parking time instantly or pay in advance for time that they can use later • Receive push notifications 10 minutes before the parking time expires • Extend the parking time remotely • See when and how much they need to pay for parking • Access all their previous transactions
Entity Name	DAEM S.A.
Logo	
Role	DAEM is the main pilot partner responsible for designing and preparing the pilot activities in line with the city and citizens requirements and current challenges, testing the solution proposed by AI4PP in the City of Athens targeting the civic engagement objective and providing evaluation and assessment results. DAEM S.A. (City of Athens IT Company) is the oldest and most significant Local Government IT Company, as it has been operating since 1983, aimed at providing Cloud based multiplatform e-Governance to local government organizations, public administration and other authorities and organizations. The development and promotion of new innovative services which are fundamental to the smart and sustainable city idea, lies at the heart of DAEM's interest and is a strategic objective at the city level. DAEM constitutes one of the most solid links in the chain of implementation and support of two-way communication nodes with citizens, residents, and visitors of the city. At the same time, it significantly contributes to the digital convergence of the operational standards of the City of Athens with those of other European Municipalities.
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Entity Type	Private for-profit organisation

3.2.1 Use Case #1 – Maintenance Policies Optimization

Use Case #1	
Use Case Name	Maintenance policies optimization
Summary	This use case will develop and validate policies for the optimal allocation of maintenance resources (e.g., workers, vehicles, materials), as well as for scheduling of different maintenance activities in the city.

<p>Description</p>	<p>This use case will develop and validate policies for the optimal allocation of maintenance resources (e.g., workers, vehicles, materials), as well as for scheduling of different activities in the city. The production of policies will take into account different parameters such as the type of infrastructure, the time needed for repair, the frequency of maintenance problems of specific types and in specific locations, possible bottleneck, as well as citizens' feedback on their satisfaction for the maintenance process and outcomes.</p>
<p>Value Proposition(s)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reduce time in resolving reported incidents ● Reduce the average cost per incident for the city ● Increase citizen satisfaction for the infrastructure maintenance activities
<p>Image(s)</p>	
<p>Keywords</p>	<p>Infrastructure maintenance, resource allocation, process optimization, citizen satisfaction</p>

3.2.2 Use Case #2 – Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development

<p>Use Case #2</p>	
<p>Use Case Name</p>	<p>Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development</p>
<p>Summary</p>	<p>This use case will be based on the execution of AI analytics over transport data (notably parking information) as a means of providing citizens with predictions about parking availability in the different areas of the city, as well as providing to the city a tool for optimal use of city-parking resources.</p>
<p>Description</p>	<p>This use case will be based on the execution of AI analytics over transport data (notably parking information) as a means of providing citizens with prediction about parking availability in the different areas of the city. Taking into account historical data about parking spaces availability, fines imposed, fares paid and more, the AI4PublicPolicy tools will be used to recommend to citizens optimal tactics for finding parking spaces (e.g., locations with high-availability), as well as for optimizing their parking payments (i.e. fares during specific times of day and for specific locations). Citizens' feedback will be solicited in order to fine-tune the data-driven policies and the related</p>

	<p>recommendations. Likewise, the VPME will be used to identify policies for the creation/allocation of parking spaces for the citizens (i.e., identifying areas where there is sufficient availability of spaces and other locations where more parking zones are needed to be created).</p>
<p>Value Proposition(s)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increased citizen satisfaction from the smart parking activities ▪ Increased revenue from parking ▪ Improved average parking availability ▪ Improved “fill rate” and occupancy for the parking positions.
<p>Image(s)</p>	<p>The image shows a mobile application interface for 'myAthensPass'. It is divided into three main sections: 'ACTIVATE PARKING', 'PARKING ACTIVE', and 'MESSAGES'. - ACTIVATE PARKING: Features a duration selector (30', 60', 90', 120', 150', 180'), 'Parking Cost' (€0.5), 'Remaining funds' (€2.5), a license plate input field (IBH4303), and a 'Parking Spot Number' input field. A large green button at the bottom says 'PARKING ACTIVATION'. - PARKING ACTIVE: Displays 'Parking Active' status, 'Parking Date' (03/06/2021 13:45), 'Duration' (30'), 'Ticket cost' (€0.50), 'License Plate' (IBH4303), and 'Address' (Ermou 103, Athina 105 55, Greece). It includes a map showing the location and an 'Expires in' timer (00:29:49). Buttons for 'Cancel ticket' and 'Extend ticket' are visible. - MESSAGES: A notification board with a header 'ΑΠΡΟΪΚΑΙΝΗΜΕΝΑ' and a sub-header 'ΔΗΜΟΣ ΑΘΗΝΑΙΩΝ - ΔΟΚΙΜΗ INAPP'. It contains an announcement for 'myAthensPass' dated 2021-04-09 and another for 'ΔΙΑΚΟΠΗ ΗΛΕΚΤΡΟΔΟΤΗΣΗΣ' dated 2021-04-01.</p>
<p>Keywords</p>	<p>Parking space availability, parking optimization, citizen satisfaction, parking payment, parking fine</p>

3.2.3 Use Case #3 – Economic/Revenue Policies Modelling

<p>Use Case #3</p>	
<p>Use Case Name</p>	<p>Economic/Revenue Policies Modelling</p>
<p>Summary</p>	<p>This third use case will expand the previous two use cases with information about the city’s revenues from the parking and the maintenance planning. In particular, the policy models of the previous use cases will be augmented with fiscal/monetary parameters in order to identify policies that maximize the city’s revenues from the parking service, while minimizing the cost of the maintenance, service and repair activities.</p>

3.3 Pilot #2 – Genoa – Italy

<p>Pilot</p>	
<p>Pilot Name</p>	<p>Citizens and Businesses Services Optimization</p>
<p>Summary</p>	<p>This pilot focuses on evidence based policies for optimizing resources used to offer support and assistance services for the citizens of the Genoa.</p>

Description	<p>The pilot will develop a policy development toolkit for the city of Genova, which will enable the public authority to extract and experiment with evidence-based policies about how to optimally organize the operations of the various citizen facing services and department of the municipality. The toolkit will be integrated in the virtualized platform of the project i.e., it will be an instance of the cloud-based VPME customized to the needs of the municipality of the Genova. It will comprise datasets derived from the SEGNALACI ² infrastructure and its (digital) interfaces to the various departments and systems of the municipality, as well as citizens' feedback that will be collected through various channels. The pilot will integrate various AI tools, including tools for analysing citizens' feedback, but mainly tools for data-driven policy recommendation, policy simulation and benchmarking. Based on this tool, the pilot system will extract and recommend policies and initiatives for allocating resources and organizing the operations of the different departments of the municipality.</p>
Motivation	<p>The Municipality of Genova as local authority is the biggest city in the Liguria Region and the third city in the Northern Italy and it is the main Italian port. One of the main strategic goals of the municipality is to facilitate the relationship between the Public Administration and local actors (citizens, businesses). In the scope of this strategic target, the municipality has established a variety of electronic channels and ICT tools that are aimed at boosting the interactions between citizens/businesses and the municipality. These channels and tools include the website of the municipality, as well as social media, which are increasingly used to facilitate citizens' and businesses' contacts with public bodies. Furthermore, the city uses popular instant messaging platforms (i.e., WhatsApp and Instagram) as official communication channels that complement other channels used by other stakeholders (e.g., the Civil Protection in Genova uses SMS and Telegram channels for sending alert messages to citizens). One of the most recent projects of the municipality is the development of the SegnalaCI platform that enables citizens to reach most of the Municipal Services and Departments. This project aimed at consolidating and unifying all the different contact centres of the Municipality, as a means of facilitating citizens' communications, in particular suggestions and reports functional to improve the quality of the municipal services, easing the appropriate routing of request and providing citizens with more effective answers about their reports, warnings and needs. In addition to routing requests, the SegnalaCI platform is being interconnected with other channels and tools (e.g., social media, web site) in order to broaden the options offered to citizens for interacting with the Municipality about possible questions, complaints, proposals. While the SegnalaCI platform facilitates citizens-city interactions through a single entry point, it does not guarantee the provision of effective responses to the citizens' warnings and reports and related improved services to citizens and businesses. The latter require the identification of optimal strategies for handling user requests, including optimal workflows and properly trained employees that will provide service to citizens. In this context, the SegnalaCI project is an invaluable source of information about citizens reports and requests, as well as the workflows employed in response to them. Likewise, it can provide information about the types of issues raised by citizens, the time it took to fulfil them, the resources (including the employees) engaged in their handling and more. As such it can serve as a basis for the development of data-driven policies about the planning of the citizens' and</p>

² <https://segnalazioni.comune.genova.it>

	<p>businesses’ services, including insights on how resources can be optimally allocated, what kind of training should be provided to employees, how the different services and departments must be organized and more. Nevertheless, the above-listed information is currently underexploited, which is a missed opportunity for the Municipality of Genova.</p> <p>Evaluation and Benchmarking Alternative Service Handling Workflows</p> <p>As part of this use case, GENOA will use the policy toolkit for providing data-driven recommendations about how different configurations of internal processes (i.e., workflows) perform when handling requests for citizen services. Specifically, ML/DL techniques will be used to extract rules about the steps entailed in handling a request. Different process configurations will be considered based on the data about citizens’ and businesses’ requests, their types and citizens’ satisfaction feedback.</p>
	Place(s)
Place Name	Genoa, Italy
Place Location	Palazzo Tursi, Via Garibaldi 9, 16124 Genoa, Italy
Characterisation	Several tools and channels aimed at facilitating the relationship between the Municipality and local actors (citizens, businesses) and at boosting their interactions, such as the institutional website and social media, as well as popular instant messaging platforms (i.e., WhatsApp and Instagram) as official communication and the Unique Phone Number (i.e. 010.10.10) enabling citizens to reach most of the Municipal Services and Departments.
Entity Name	Municipality of Genoa
Logo	
Role	Local Authority
Address	Palazzo Tursi, Via Garibaldi 9, 16124 Genoa, Italy
Website	https://smart.comune.genova.it/
Contact(s)	Dr. Alessandra Risso
Entity Type	Public Organisation

3.3.1 Use Case #1 – Reducing Road Accidents against Vulnerable People

Use Case #1	
Use Case Name	Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people
Summary	This use case will execute ML/DL techniques to determine the danger index of city areas for the various vulnerable categories (pedestrians, cyclists, motorcyclists) in relation to possible causes (time, weather, environment, morphology, traffic, ...) in order to provide information and predictive analysis to decide and justify actions and interventions functional to reduce road accidents against vulnerable subjects.
Description	The Interministerial Committee for Economic Planning and Sustainable Development (CIPESS) approved the National Road Safety Plan (NSSP) 2030 on 14 April 2022. The new National Road Safety Plan adopts the “Safe

System” approach proposed by the European Commission and the UN 2030 Agenda, which aims to reduce the number of road fatalities and serious injuries by 50% by 2030 compared to 2019 and to zero by 2050. A key innovation of the UNDP 2030 is the definition of specific strategies for risk categories with targeted actions for each of them. The categories considered to be at greatest risk are: children and adolescents, young drivers, the over-65s, cyclists, pedestrians and users of powered two-wheelers. We are still waiting for the text to be made public. This will be followed by the adoption of individual implementation programmes that will define the details of the targeted interventions. In order to achieve the objectives of reducing road accidents and injuries it is necessary to intervene on the phenomenon with an analytical and dynamic approach. In the city of Genoa the traditional road safety interventions are undertaken by the decision makers, using the expertise of the technical bodies in charge, which refer to statistical elaborations that start from the data of accident events processed in an empirical way and not connected with other context elements that could increase the correct understanding of the events. It is therefore desirable to use an artificial intelligence tool that can provide useful information to be able to make decisions also on the basis of predictive elements to support decision-making policies. Artificial intelligence can in fact analyse and compose complex scenarios, which are impossible for human intelligence to process, and offer useful modelling to identify locations or risk dynamics. The improvement of the context analysis will be made possible by the assumption of additional data to those currently available and processed by the Local Police, with the implementation of additional data provided by the different structures operating in the field of road safety and that will systemise such data in the context of the local partnership. This will allow the construction of scenarios through the elaboration of artificial intelligence that will make available the potential derived from the large amount of data put into system. Through this information, the public administrator will have an advantage in evaluating the decisions to be implemented. A system designed in this way can allow moments of virtual involvement of citizens on the problem analysed, on the perception of the risk and on the sharing of the policies undertaken. The use of artificial intelligence will allow the processing of a complex amount of data, with analyses that man would do with enormous effort or would never be able to do. The optimisation of the processing times and the articulation of different sources of context, will be able to increase the knowledge of the phenomenon of road accidents in a sensitive way. It will be necessary to build a model that determines the danger index of the city areas for the various vulnerable categories (pedestrians, cyclists, motorcyclists) in relation to possible causes (time, weather, environment, morphology, traffic, ...) this will make it possible to provide information and predictive analysis to decide and justify, for example:

- Inspections
- Maintenance interventions
- Speed limit reduction
- Installation of remote speed control devices
- Traffic modifications
- Road closures at certain times or weather conditions/forecasts

Value Proposition(s)	Evaluating the danger index of city areas in relation to possible causes. Extracting information and predictive analysis to decide and justify actions and interventions for reducing road accidents against vulnerable subjects.
Website	https://smart.comune.genova.it/
Keywords	Danger of city areas, vulnerable people, predictive analysis, increased safety.

3.3.2 Use Case #2 – Optimizing the Allocation and Use of Resources for Social and Demographic Services also via fostering the interoperability between information systems

Use Case #2	
Use Case Name	Optimizing the Allocation and Use of Resources for Social and Demographic Services also via fostering the interoperability between information systems
Summary	This use case will execute ML/DL techniques over data about the citizens' requests for services and their handling workflows, towards identify optimal allocation of human resources and other assets (e.g., machines, equipment, software/hardware), in particular as regards two offices: social services office and demographic services office. As for the social services, in this direction it is key to evaluate how to improve the interoperability with wider systems (e.g. Regional or INPS DBs), for the efficiency of resources and the development of evidence-based policies. As for the demographic/registry services, efforts will be directed especially to the analysis and re-engineering of the transversal work process dealing in particular with registry office changes.
Description	<p>Within the framework of this use case, the intention is to identify optimal allocation of human resources and other assets (e.g., machines, equipment, software/hardware) related to the social and demographic services office and to evaluate the opportunities of interoperability with wider systems (e.g., Regional or INPS DBs), for the efficiency of resources and the development of evidence-based policies. It appears essential to be able to implement a process aimed at consolidating the existing system, also in relation to interoperability with broader systems. This analysis, in particular as regards the social services office, could also be preparatory to the possible subsequent development of the following actions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Analysis, design and possible implementation of a product that facilitates the interoperability of other systems, both within and outside the Public Administration, with the Social Policies information system; 2) Design of a data repository, with a good level of alignment/update of the developed data batteries, connecting with tools used by the Administration; 3) Construction of strategic reading models of the collected data, with a specific territorialization and the possibility of longitudinal reading; 4) Return of useful information to the public decision-maker, through several options of proposals for "intelligent" analysis of the collected data. <p>The outcome of the toolkit will be a set of data-driven recommendations and rules about how to best allocate and use resources for social and demographic services and enhance interoperability between information systems in order to make optimal use of resources, minimize service times and increase citizens' satisfaction.</p>

	As for the demographic/registry services, the focus will be on the analysis and re-engineering of the transversal work process of the registry offices that deal in particular with registry office changes (immigrations, changes of residence, changes in civil status, AIRE registrations, etc.) with the aim of channelling citizens' requests, also by simplifying access to the portal, improving the ability to respond to citizens and internal communication between registry offices, including the multi-purpose desk. These are online practices. There is also a communication initiative towards citizens.
Value Proposition(s)	Optimizing the Allocation and Use of Resources for Social and Demographic/Registry Services, improvement of services to citizens and analysis towards the improvement of interoperability
Website	https://smart.comune.genova.it/
Keywords	Social services, resources, optimization, citizens' satisfaction

3.3.3 Use Case #3 – More effective extraordinary maintenance interventions by enhancing the “SegnalaCI” Citizens’ Suggestions/Reports and Policies Visualizations

Use Case #3	
Use Case Name	More effective extraordinary maintenance interventions by enhancing the “SegnalaCI” Citizens’ Suggestions/Reports and Policies Visualizations
Summary	This use case will improve the planning and deployment of extraordinary maintenance interventions also by an enhanced exploitation of the functionalities offered by the SegnalaCI platform. It allows to visualize data about citizens’ suggestions and reports sent through the SegnalaCI platform and about the workflows for handling them in an interactive map/dashboard. Information about the type, location, handling times, citizen demographics etc. associated with each request will be displayed and provided to both policy makers (inside the municipality) and citizens. The dashboard will be used to increase the transparency, trustworthiness, and accountability of the policy development process.
Description	Through the SegnalaCi platform, citizens can make suggestions and reports to the Municipality of Genoa on a map (OpenStreetMap) in order to improve the quality of the services offered by the Administration itself and to improve the livability of the City, as well as to execute useful effective extraordinary maintenance interventions. In order to carry out the reporting activity and then use the SegnalaCI platform it is necessary to authenticate through Spid (public digital identity system) or register for the first time and thus obtain username and password, with which it will then be possible to make subsequent accesses. It is also possible to use the application via smartphone or tablet. Citizens can provide proposals, suggestions, and reports on the map. In particular, suggestion means any proposal or communication, even of appreciation, by the citizen aimed at improving the quality of the services offered, whilst reporting means communication by the citizen regarding critical situations and / or malfunctions (eg signs, public lighting, holes in the streets, etc ...). The "report" is taken over by the municipal operators, who will forward to the responsible persons responsible for the matter within 48 hours, on weekdays. The answer will be provided on average within 15 days. With the official response from the institution, the report is closed. If the requested or suggested intervention has been deemed useful, necessary, and economically sustainable by the service manager, it

will be included in the Administration's programs, on the basis of the priorities decided by the body itself and according to the methods and times defined independently by the Office. This service has been in use since November 2020, when 200 volunteer citizens began to test the platform in advance. Since January 4, 2021, the platform has been open to all citizens. Since the opening, 2193 new citizens have registered. In recent weeks, the number of registered citizens has increased and also the number of reports forwarded to the Administration through ReportCi: the greatest number of reports concerns the facility, the environment, PL and mobility.

This use case will visualize data about this citizens' suggestions and reports and about the workflows for handling them, with a focus on extraordinary maintenance interventions (on flowerbed borders, city squares and pedestrian areas, pavements and stairways, street mowing, etc.) and the overall Maintenance Plan of the Municipality of Genoa, in an interactive map/dashboard. Information about the type, location, handling times, citizen demographics etc. associated with each suggestion and report will be displayed and provided to both policy makers (inside the municipality) and citizens. The dashboard will be used to increase the transparency, trustworthiness, and accountability of the policy development process.

SegnalaCI's functionalities might also be enriched to cover the citizens' feedback on how their reports and/or suggestions have been addressed by the Municipality.

The VPME will provide the means for using the AI policy development tools of the above use cases at a strategic level. Hence, they will facilitate not only the creation/formulation of policies, but also their reprogramming and reconfiguration as well. All policy development use cases will engage both citizens and policy makers from CDG. Furthermore, as part of the pilot, the project will also study and implement the required organizational transformation activities.

Value Proposition(s)

Improvement of the planning and execution of the extraordinary maintenance interventions, as well as the outcomes and value of SegnalaCI Platform

Image(s)

Website	https://segnalazioni.comune.genova.it/
Keywords	Report, suggestions, municipal offices

3.4 Pilot #3 – Nicosia - Cyprus

Pilot	
Pilot Name	Effective Policies for Holistic Mobility and Accessibility
Summary	This pilot will provide data-driven evidence-based policies for optimizing mobility in Nicosia. Public Transport is generally lacking in Cyprus, affecting citizens wellbeing and also CO2 emissions. Usage and bus frequency need to be enhanced to increase use from the public. To this end, this pilot will enhance: (A) The Nicosia Smart City platform with AI4PublicPolicy functionalities and (B) The mobility and accessibility processes of the city with data-driven insights from the analysis of data from the city’s platform.
Description	<p>AI4PublicPolicy will provide Nicosia Municipality with access to customized instance of the project’s VPME that will enable the public authority to extract and evaluate data-driven urban mobility policies. The policies will consider information about bus routes and itineraries, as well as information about the occupancy of parking spaces in the city. Attention will be paid on mobility policies including elderly and disabled individuals through the development of data-driven policies for inclusiveness zones around bus stops and parking spaces that are used from elderly and disabled individuals.</p> <p>Mobility optimization policies will be targeted based on the consideration of alternative urban transport options in multi-modal scenarios and the optimization of parameters such as cost-effectiveness, sustainability and citizens’ satisfaction. To this end, the pilot will create analytics models about urban transport and mobility policies, while leveraging AI algorithms in order to identify the parameters that lead to optimal policies. The policies will assume an integrated environment, where different mobility options (e.g., car, bus) are interconnected and different optimization criteria (e.g., accessibility, time/speed, cost) are considered.</p>
Motivation	<p>One of the most recent and strategic projects of Nicosia Municipality, involves the development, deployment, and operation of a Smart City platform. The platform is one of the main tools of the digital transformation of the city. It collects and aggregates data from multiple sources (e.g., city sensors, transport systems city information databases) to enable a range of smart applications with emphasis on revitalizing certain areas and planning an integrated urban development. It can also enable the development of data-driven citizen-centric applications for specific groups such as elderly and disabled systems.</p> <p>The city population residing within the old city is ageing. Their needs include accessible and effective mobility, using their cars and/or public transport such as the bus services of the municipality. In this direction, the city is developing policies that foster inclusive mobility, such as accessible bus stops and parking spaces for disabled. In this context, the Smart City platform enables the municipality to develop and optimize such policies. Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning can be very powerful tools for the development of such policies.</p>
	Place(s)
Place Name	Nicosia, Cyprus

Place Location	Nicosia, Cyprus
Characterisation	Smart mobility
Entity Name	Nicosia Municipality
Logo	Δήμος Λευκωσίας Nicosia Municipality
Role	End-user, Data Provider
Address	Eleftheria Square, Nicosia, Cyprus
Website	https://www.nicosia.org.cy/en-GB/home/
Contact(s)	Charis Theocharous
Entity Type	Public organization

3.4.1 Use Case #1 – Optimal urban mobility policies for citizens

Use Case #1	
Use Case Name	Optimal urban mobility policies for citizens
Summary	This use case will extract and provide to citizens data-driven optimal policies about their mobility in the cities.
Description	Leveraging data about bus routes & occupancy, parking usage, and citizens' preferences, this use case will create optimal mobility policies for buses and parking spaces, notably policies that reduce travel times and travel costs in multi-modal transport scenarios combining bus, car, and walking transport modalities. The proposed policies will provide recommendations about the frequency of buses at certain times of the day/week and the planning of parking spaces to ensure availability for the citizens. One of the main innovations of the use case will be the use of machine learning and XAI to provide passenger centered recommendations of optimal mobility options, which is typically lacking in smart mobility solutions. Citizens' feedback will be received and integrated using surveys and co-creation sessions.
Value Proposition(s)	Evidence-based policies that enable citizens to move faster, save time, cost and improve the city's environmental performance.
Image(s)	
Website	https://cyprus-mail.com/2022/02/08/nicosia-municipality-installs-smart-city-cameras-along-main-roads/ https://www.nicosia.org.cy/en-GB/municipality/services/cashier/parking/

	https://www.publictransport.com.cy/routes/page/routes-and-timetables
Keywords	Evidence Driven Policies, Urban Mobility, Sustainable Mobility, Cost-Effective Mobility

3.4.2 Use Case #2 – Optimal Urban mobility policies for the Municipality

Use Case #2	
Use Case Name	Optimal Urban mobility policies for the Municipality
Summary	This use case will recommend/introduce policies that optimize city’s goals such as sustainability and transport operational cost, while taking into account citizens’ feedback and satisfaction.
Description	This use case will produce urban mobility policies that optimize resources (e.g., bus itineraries, parking spaces revenue) and environmental performance (e.g., CO2 emissions, fuel consumption). In this direction, it will leverage CO2/environmental measurements from the Smart City platform, information about bus routes and travel times, as well as estimates about fuel consumption and the environmental impact of different modes of mobility. Citizens’ feedback will be received and integrated using surveys and co-creation sessions.
Value Proposition(s)	Improved environmental performance for the city; Improved Resources management and optimization
Image(s)	
Website	https://cyprus-mail.com/2022/02/08/nicosia-municipality-installs-smart-city-cameras-along-main-roads/ https://www.nicosia.org.cy/en-GB/municipality/services/cashier/parking/ https://www.publictransport.com.cy/routes/page/routes-and-timetables
Keywords	Citizen-Driven Policies, Evidence Driven Policies, Urban Mobility, Sustainable Mobility, Cost-Effective Mobility

3.4.3 Use Case #3 – Accessible urban mobility policies

Use Case #3	
Use Case Name	Accessible urban mobility policies
Summary	This use cases will target people with disabilities towards improving their accessibility to the mobility services of the municipality and their overall inclusion in the city’s transport ecosystem.

Description	This use case will create inclusiveness zones around bus stops and parking spaces for disabled people. These zones will aim at optimizing the overall health environment (e.g., CO2, noise) for the citizens, while offering them the best possible quality of service. Leveraging historical data about bus stops and parking spaces, the municipality will specify policies for improving the health environment (e.g., noise reduction policies/fines on local shops, CO2 reduction policies), as well as policies for improving the offered services (e.g., deployment of inclusiveness agent) and the surrounding environment (e.g., tree planting).
Value Proposition(s)	Improved accessibility, inclusiveness and sustainability of urban mobility services; Higher satisfaction for elderly, disabled or handicapped citizens
Image(s)	N/A
Website	N/A
Keywords	Accessibility, Sustainability, Mobility, Citizens-Centric Policies

3.5 Pilot #4 – Lisbon - Portugal

Pilot	
Pilot Name	Energy Management Policies
Summary	With the growing data availability, new and different approaches on standard decision-making process can lead to more accurate decisions and solutions. In Lisbon, it is assumed that themes focused by SECAP, such as climate and energy management, can be tackled with a new framework. Therefore, this Pilot focus on gathering relevant and valid data sources and, with the aid of AI and machine learning algorithms, detect patterns and problems regarding energy efficiency, air quality or climate conditions, so that possible data-driven policies and services can be defined to ensure a more sustainable and efficient environment in the city.
Description	The pilot focus on gathering relevant and valid data sources, such as weather, buildings’ characteristics, and energy consumption, and with the aid of AI and machine learning algorithms detect patterns and problems regarding energy efficiency, so that possible data-driven policies can be defined to ensure a more sustainable and efficient environment in the city. An approach focused on the SECAP component will be implemented, based on the following activities: (i) Gathering data on energy consumption and production, particularly at building level, using IoT and smart meters technologies; (ii) Analysing and integrating energy consumption data with other relevant existing data (such as current buildings conditions/archetypes and weather data); (iii) Using the project’s AI-based tools (integrated within the VPME) to provide guidance on better energy-efficient solutions and inform about consumption and production patterns. Data regarding energy consumption will be gathered using smart meters and IoT devices. Apart from the current energy consumption time interval of 15 minutes, with the implementation of IoT devices, a deeper analysis will be made, to analyse specific types of energy consumption in each building, assuming a breakdown of consumption considering the equipment existing in each delivery point. Data regarding buildings archetypes is gathered with the support from other projects of LIS. With these main data sources, AI models can be implemented to analyse patterns and support policy making on general energy performance improvement. Deep Learning models such as Long short-term memory network (LSTM Network), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Deep

	<p>Belief Networks (DBNs) can be also used to provide forecast on energy consumption. Clustering algorithms, e.g., k-Means, Hierarchical Cluster Analysis and Expectation Maximization can be used to group clients on similar energy usage. Other deep learning models, such as deep neural networks, can be used to detect patterns on the behaviour of different buildings. With the definition of different patterns in buildings, and with the integration of the different information layers (such as real weather data and energy consumption data), it is possible to create and analyse common behavioural scenarios on each archetype of buildings to better understand real energy performance. This information can be used for data-driven decisions on policies for energy efficiency.</p>
Motivation	<p>Aware of the huge pression by the growing urban population, local governments all over the world are formally signing the Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy, the world's largest movement for local climate and energy actions. Covenant signatories commit to adopting an integrated approach to climate change mitigation and adaptation, whereas most of them set as vision carbon neutrality by 2050, in alignment with the Paris goals. Signatories are required to develop, within the first two years of adhesion, a Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP) with the aims of cutting CO₂ emissions by at least 40% by 2030 and increasing resilience to climate change. These bold political commitments mark the beginning of a long-term process with cities committed to reporting on the implementation progress of their plans every two years. However, designing, implementing, and monitoring a SECAP is a complex task. The mitigation goals and strategies required for promoting energy efficiency in end-use sectors are not only difficult to establish, but also to implement and monitor. Therefore, cities urge for available tools and methods that support them in these difficult tasks. The city of Lisbon is currently faced with similar challenges and is considering data-driven solutions for the elicitation of evidence-based policies. With growing data availability, new and different approaches on standard decision-making process can lead to more accurate solutions. In Lisbon, buildings' energy efficiency is a problem that can be tackled with a new framework.</p>
	Place(s)
Place Name	Lisbon, Portugal
Place Location	Lisbon, Portugal
Characterisation	<p>Lisbon follows a typical Mediterranean city model and, as such, it shares most of the common challenges of this kind of cities. Its urban fabric is strongly adapted to medieval structures; a substantial part of the city is composed by narrow streets with few green public spaces; it is populated mostly by elderly inhabitants and experiences massive tourism fluxes; congested streets with excessive use of private cars posing serious impacts on air pollution and noise, GHG emissions and human health; loss of the sense of community, hampering the authenticity of its different districts; etc. In addition to these, over the last few decades, Lisbon has lost a third of its residents, as a result of uncontrolled urban development - urban sprawl in the suburbs coupled with depopulation and decaying neighbourhoods in the historic centre. This has obviously led to a deterioration of the quality of life in the city. With the previous challenges in mind, the Municipality has invested in the regeneration of the city, bearing in mind the importance of the environment and people's wellbeing. Within this scope, several strategic plans have been defined, most of them created through participative processes, highlighting its commitment towards a true citizen centric, open innovation city. Specifically, on energy</p>

	<p>efficiency Lisbon's vision is focused on an integrated approach for energy consumption and production. This approach includes applied innovation, better planning, more participation, higher energy efficiency, better transport solutions, and intelligent use of Information and Communication Technologies. Current plans for the city include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • strongly promote nZEB and nZEC concepts; • explore all renewable energy sources (solar thermal and photovoltaic energy, and wind power); • explore synergies of the energy-water nexus; • explore synergies between energy and mobility; <p>Regarding climate and air quality conditions, the city has recently installed a network of sensors, composed by over 650 sensors in 80 different locations, and measuring the following parameters: particles (PM2.5 and PM10), carbon monoxide (CO), sulfur dioxide (SO2), nitrogen dioxide (NO2), nitrogen oxide (NO), ozone (O3), benzene (C2H6), level equivalent continuous sound, atmospheric pressure, relative humidity, wind, rainfall, temperature, global radiation, ultraviolet radiation and medium traffic. Through this monitoring network, the goal is to reinforce the diagnosis of the city environment in terms of air quality and climate conditions, map priority areas for intervention, invest in the public information component and encourage the adoption of more sustainable behaviours, as well as support the definition of more appropriate measures to mitigate the negative effects of potential episodes of atmospheric pollution (air quality and noise) and extreme weather events. Moreover, the Municipality is currently developing and implementing its own data platform. This aims to be an ICT 'smart city' management platform to provide innovative tools for collaborative management of data, at city level. As any other city platforms, this includes several modules, layers and tools and, currently, hundreds of datasets are being already processed in this platform, allowing for instance the operational integrated control system between several local entities (Civil Protection, Fire Brigades, Police, etc.) with the municipal operational services.</p>
Entity Name	Lisboa E-Nova
Logo	
Role	Energy and Environmental Agency - a non-profit association, operating under private law, that seeks to contribute to the sustainable development of the city of Lisbon and its metropolitan area.
Address	Rua dos Fanqueiros, 38 – 2º Andar - 1100-231 Lisboa
Website	https://lisboanova.org
Contact(s)	<p>Maria Rodrigues</p> <p>António Sequeira</p> <p>Eduardo Silva</p> <p>Sara Freitas</p>
Entity Type	Other

3.5.1 Use Case #1 – Renewables (PV) Potential and Performance Analysis

Use Case #1	
Use Case Name	Renewables (PV) potential and performance analysis
Summary	This use case will identify existing assets and assess the potential renewables (PV) production.
Description	This use case aims to identify the PV systems existing in the city as well as create methods to assess and determine accurately their production potential. In a first stage, the goal will be to identify and locate the PV systems installed in the city in order to understand about the current energy production performance in the city and infer about the city's PV adoption curve through time. These analytics should be made by using different available datasets, including orthophotomaps, satellite images, and others available, as well as those provided by existing platforms (e.g., Solis platform). In a second stage, this use case should provide users with the ability to monitor PV energy production potential, ideally by defining time series and forecast scenarios (e.g., on "day-ahead"; "month ahead"; "quarter ahead", etc.). This aims to enable the definition of scenarios elucidating about the achievement of city's defined goals and targets for 2030, as well as to inform building(s) owner(s) and citizens about the potential PV production of their buildings, as well as to provide with estimates about potential cost savings.
Keywords	Energy performance, renewables, PV production and forecast.

3.5.2 Use Case #2 – Buildings Energy Performance Analysis

Use Case #2	
Use Case Name	Buildings Energy Performance Analysis
Summary	This use case will identify problems in the buildings' energy performance and will perform root cause analysis.
Description	This use case aims to provide user with the ability to better understand about the buildings' energy performance. Considering the data availability, the focus should be at defining buildings insulation capacity at the roof level (i.e., thermal insulation performance) and to assess how external variables (e.g. temperature, humidity, solar exposure) influence buildings energy performance/consumption. The goals are manifold and include: understanding about energy performance of existing buildings, that will drive the analysis on city's investment needs, and (possibly) support definition of potential financial mechanisms (UC#3); to understand how energy consumption varies with meteorological variables through root cause analysis; and to better understand about the impacts of different energy related interventions performed in the buildings (monitoring analysis), which can be used to better plan future interventions.
Keywords	Buildings, Energy performance, ...

3.5.3 Use Case #3 – Budget Planning for Energy Usage and Buildings Renovation

Use Case #3	
Use Case Name	Budget Planning for Energy Usage and Buildings Renovation

Summary	This use cases will focus on policy making decisions on budget planning and effective use of budget and public resources towards buildings renovation and energy usage. For instance, policies for the definition of specific financial supporting mechanisms or retrofit schemes will be recommended.
Description	This use case is partially a consequence of UC#2. Its goal is to provide the user with the ability to better estimate about investment needs regarding the city built environment and support the definition of priorities for potential local financial mechanisms aimed at increasing buildings energy efficiency and city's overall energy performance.
Keywords	Urban thermal variations, Urban heat island, urban air quality monitoring

3.5.4 Use Case #4 – City’s Thermal and Air Quality Performance

Use Case #4	
Use Case Name	City’s thermal and air quality performance
Summary	This use cases will focus on providing visual and interactive support to understand temperature and air quality variations throughout the city.
Description	This use case aims to take advantage from the networks of sensors installed in the city that, together with other information source, should provide the user with the ability to map air temperature and air quality variations throughout the city. The goal is to understand the city thermal and air quality performance, locate the main hot spots and infer the reasons through root cause analysis, as well as to elucidate about ‘urban heat island’ effects and the locations exposed to higher concentrations of pollutants. In addition, the provision of this information to citizens is also intended, allowing for instance better planning trips to a specific point in the city according to current temperatures and/or pollutants exposure levels.
Keywords	Urban thermal variations, Urban heat island, urban air quality monitoring

3.5.5 Use Case #5 – City’s Greenhouse Gases Emissions

Use Case #5	
Use Case Name	City’s greenhouse gases emissions
Summary	This use cases will focus on assessing city’s carbon capture and storage capacity and provide estimates on non-CO ₂ greenhouse gases.
Description	This use case aims to realize the carbon capture and storage capacity of the city’s green and river areas, in order to support and better determine carbon balance assessments and progression through time. By using data past and current time series, this should provide the user with the ability to understand the potential impact of the green areas created in the recent years as well as their influence for the carbon emissions balance. Focusing on the non-CO ₂ greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions, the goal is to determine emission and concentration levels, supporting the monitoring of development policies with more accurate information, as well as to be able to better monitor defined goal related to GHG inventory.
Keywords	GHG inventories; GHG monitoring; non-CO ₂ greenhouse gases monitoring; Carbon capture and storage.

3.6 3.6 – Pilot #5 – Burgas – Bulgaria

Pilot	
Pilot Name	Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance Policies
Summary	The pilot will develop a data-driven policy making tool for the maintenance of the water management infrastructure through data gathered from the infrastructure itself via fiber optic devices installed with no dig techniques.
Description	At the heart of the tool will be Data-driven methods based on the application of AI or machine learning algorithms and deep learning methods. These methods, after being properly trained with data sets, can extract information, detect patterns, and make calculations and predictions leading to improving directly or indirectly water management. The digital transformation of water supply supports the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), especially SDG 6: Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all; and SDG 13: Climate Action, by taking urgent actions to promote climate-related investments to combat climate change impacts. In the later direction, the pilot will benefit from the involvement of EKSO, which is a developer of smart pipes that have embedded grids of Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) from the production stage. EKSO has experience with water pipes sensor data acquisition and is willing to develop the analysis towards data-driven LCA. In the scope of the AI4PP pilot, EKSO and BURGAS will collaborate in the development of a policy making tools that will create and evaluate water pipes maintenance plans, based on data-driven insights about the infrastructure (e.g., information about diameter and material of the pipes, water flow rate, pressure and velocity, etc...) and its operative condition (i.e., leveraging EKSO pipes). The pilot will build and validate policy models that will reduce physical and commercial water losses and maintenance cost, while helping the municipality establish effective maintenance and repair schedules/policies. The project's tools will recommend, simulate, and benchmark policies associated with pipe/water data measurement. Based on the results and experience, the AI pilot can be upscaled to wider portions of the water distribution system.
Motivation	Burgas municipality has been heavily investing in the development of a safe and efficient water supply and sanitation infrastructures, as reflected in recent initiatives, including: (i) The provision of a 32.4 million EUR loan to Burgas Water Company (BWC), which is aimed at the co-financing investments in the infrastructure Burgas WSSO is a state-owned company and sole provider of water supply, wastewater collection and treatment services in the Burgas region; (ii) The recent (March 2021) approval of an investment of over €63 million EUR from the Cohesion Fund to provide better access to drinking water and improved sewerage for the people living in the district of Burgas. The main goal of these projects is to increase the efficiency of the water management infrastructure, to cut its operating costs, as well as to align it with national and EU drinking water, wastewater collection and treatment and sludge disposal legislation. The impact of the projects will be very high, as it will offer thousands of inhabitants in the greater Burgas area with access to a more reliable water supply, which will also handle pollution loads. Along with the establishment of this infrastructure, the municipality of Burgas is interested in establishing proper policies for the maintenance, service, and repair of the water management infrastructure, which will boost its operational efficiency, will reduce leakages and will optimize operational management. The municipality and the WSSO aspire to reduce water losses, and exploit water management policies which have a significant socio-economic impact,

	as lost water could have been used for plumbing, drinking, bathing, and better irrigation. In this direction, the municipality believes that it could benefit from the advent of digital technologies for managing critical infrastructures, including analysis and optimization of their lifecycle.
	Place(s)
Place Name	City of Burgas Bulgaria
Place Location	Bulgaria, District of Burgas, City of Burgas
Characterisation	Population of 226 179 citizens and area of 254 sq.km. The WSSO service area is served by 517 km water supply networks and 404 km sewage networks.
Entity Name	Burgas Municipality
Logo	
Role	Burgas Municipality is the main pilot partner and will be responsible for the coordination and engagement of all the interested parties in the pilot activities for ensuring that they follow the citizens' needs and those of the city. It will test the solution proposed by AI4PP in the City of Burgas targeting the civic engagement objective and providing evaluation and assessment results for the goal of improving water-related policies of the municipality. In support of Climate adaptation, Burgas is in the frontline of the cities in Bulgaria, implementing pilots for smart management and implementation of new measures for more effective resource planning. Burgas Water Company is the only company providing the services of water supply and sewage and wastewater treatment in the district of Burgas, which is the biggest district in Bulgaria, covering 14 municipalities. The company will help with the implementation of the project activities and the data acquisition as well as resolving any technical issues related to the water utility service. The provision of high-quality water services at acceptable prices is a basic need today. It is important to the administration of the municipality that the citizens are getting sustainable and efficient in time service. To this end, it is in the municipality's high priority interest to prevent water losses, be they from operational network leakages or thefts; to ensure periodical timely and effective maintenance of the pipes; and to ensure that repair works are programmed and done quickly and with minimal disturbance to the residents and visitors of the city. Furthermore, Burgas is heavily invested in adopting the principles of sustainable development and finding and adopting smart solutions to the increasingly more complex challenges of the future, which can serve as an example to other European Municipalities and the practices of Burgas can be a replication model for others.
Address	ul. "Aleksandrovska" 26, Burgas 8000, Bulgaria
Website	www.burgas.bg
Contact(s)	Boian Popunkiov Daniela Alexieva Velichka Velikova

Entity Type	Type of organisation: Public Organization, Municipality
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3.6.1 Use Case #1 – Smart Water Management System - Pobeda Residential Neighbourhood

Use Case #1	
Use Case Name	Smart Water Management System - Pobeda Residential Neighbourhood
Summary	This use case will measure the water losses and identify those that are due to unauthorized consumption. Subsequently, it will develop data-driven policies for the prevention of damages and losses.
Description	This use case will develop data-driven policies for the maintenance of the water management infrastructure by monitoring and measuring the water inflow and using AI to analyse and process the data. The Pilot smart pipe will be installed in a zone called District Metered Area (DMA) and it has 1131 water supply connections and approximately 8200 residents. The neighbourhood was chosen because it has a predominantly Roma population and historically low rates of bill collection, assumed to be due to the low income and illegal water connections. This directly affects the operational quality of the network. Beside the various problems that could be managed, that the pilot should take into consideration, the most important is to identify directly or indirectly which losses are due to leakages and unauthorized consumption. The historically measured data will be utilized to train the AI that will later provide information on the amount and type of water losses. The AI algorithms will try to find the most likely status of the water supply network after assigning a certain degree of uncertainty to the existing data and perform a continuous calibration on the network. This will allow an analysis of the structure of the errors (difference between the measurements and predictions) at each control point, and it will allow information to be extracted from the error patterns.
Value Proposition(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ [Reduce] Physical Water Losses ▪ [Reduce] Commercial Water Losses ▪ [Improve] Water Quality ▪ [Control] Water Tariff Increases ▪ [Optimize] Capital Investment ▪ [Reduce] Operating Costs ▪ [Benefit] Consumers ▪ [Support] Sustainable Development Goals ▪ [Deliver] Better Service
Documentation	Paper reports going back 3 years from the billing system of WSSO, paper records going back 3 years of network maintenance and water loss events
Keywords	Water infrastructure, AI, water losses reduction, water quality, maintenance cost reduction, sustainable development goals, smart water technology

3.6.2 Use Case #2 – Condition-Based Monitoring and LCA for Maintenance and Repair Policies

Use Case #2	
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Use Case Name	Condition-based Monitoring and LCA for Maintenance and Repair Policies
Summary	This use case will develop data-driven policies for the maintenance of main water infrastructure.
Description	This use case will develop data-driven policies for the maintenance of main water infrastructure by monitoring and measuring the water inflow and the corresponding pressure on a continual basis for the primary water distribution network on Industrial street, which is a steel pipe with diameter of 530 millimetres and length of 1450 metres. The chosen location and pipe is known for a lot of accidents (i.e. pipe bursts) in the past and the pipe should be replaced with a new one. This will provide the AI with important, valuable, and irreplaceable information of historical data, measurements before and after the new pipe installation. The measured data will be utilized to train the AI that will later evaluate the condition of the pipe and after replacement the difference in water losses will be measured. The process will provide us with information that can later be upscaled to wider proportions of the net. This will help to identify, prioritize, and target the areas that will bring the largest benefits and at the same time reduce maintenance costs because of strategically placed efforts (e.g., installing fewer sensors and repairing or replacing the pipes with the biggest impact first).
Value Proposition(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ [Prioritize] Pipe Replacement ▪ [Optimize] Distribution Network Sectorization ▪ [Reduce] Physical Water Losses ▪ [Reduce] Commercial Water Losses ▪ [Improve] Water Quality ▪ [Control] Water Tariff Increases ▪ [Optimize] Capital Investment ▪ [Reduce] Operating Costs ▪ [Benefit] Consumers ▪ [Support] Sustainable Development Goals ▪ [Deliver] Better Service
Documentation	Paper records going back 3 years of network maintenance and water loss events
Keywords	Pipe replacement, water infrastructure, AI, water losses reduction, water quality, cost reduction, sustainable development goals, smart water technology.

4 User Stories

This chapter focus on the definition of the actual User Stories, and were defined in the form:

“As a <type of user>, I want <some goal> so that <some reason>”

The 5 Pilots target different categories. These categories are represented in the image below.

Figure 6: Pilot Categories

4.1 User Stories Overview

An overview of User Stories that were collected based on the Canvas methodology was mentioned in the second chapter. The complete list of AI4PublicPolicies User Stories is available in the Appendix (Appendix 3 – Complete List of User Stories). User Stories IDs were given by us, as we were analysing each one, to make your search easier.

Figure 7: Number of User Stories per Category

4.2 Policies for Infrastructures Maintenance and Repair

User Stories ID	User	As a «type of user», I want «some goal» so that «some reason».
		<i>Identify the costumer job(s) to which this user story relates.</i>	<i>Describe the intended goal that the user expects to be fulfilled.</i>	<i>Identify the reason(s) to which this user story relates.</i>
US01		As a Head of Urban Planning Dpt	I want to see a prediction/forecast of the completion time for each type of incident	so that I can provide a data driven feedback to citizens and the head of operations regarding the completion time
US02		As a Head of Urban Planning Dpt	I want to have a prediction of the incidents frequency per season of the year	in order to be able to plan the seasonal personnel according to forecasted needs

D2.1 – Use Case Scenarios Definition and Design

US03	As a Head of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management Dpt	i want to be able to set a route of incident fixes locations based on shortest path principle	so that i can optimize the personnel moving and vehicle costs and minimise the resolution time.
US04	As a Head of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management Dpt	I want to receive feedback from citizens about maintenance issues handling	So I can improve the issue response time and quality
US05	As a City Employee (in the Dpt of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management/Urban Planning/Urban Green Spaces and Public Lighting	I want to have a prediction of incidents occurrence frequency	So I can plan equipment / materials purchases in optimal prices (economies of scale, etc.)
US06	As a City Employee (in the Dpt of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management/Urban Planning/Urban Green Spaces and Public Lighting	I want to have an overview of the predicted maintenance needs in city assets (e.g. roads, lightning, pedestrian etc)	So I can schedule activities more efficiently
US07	As a Head of Dpt of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management/Urban Planning/Urban Green Spaces and Public Lighting	I want to have an output report on estimated predictions for the timeline, human resources and cost of maintenance of the city	So I can provide maintenance services proactively and increase QoS life in the city
US08	As a citizen	I want to be informed of the outcome of my complaint / report	So I can be sure my complaint has been addressed
US09	As a City Worker	I want to have a schedule of the foreseen maintenance and other repairing issues	So I can estimate and manage my weekly/monthly workload
US10	As a Head of Dpt of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management/Urban Planning/Urban Green Spaces and Public Lighting	I want to have a real-time idea of the teams (e.g. workers, vehicles) that are on the field.	So i can optimal scheduling of maintenance. E.g if there is something to do near the team on the field, the scheduling could be readjusted
US11	As a Head of Dpt of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management/Urban Planning/Urban Green	Classify the incident by its maintenance urgency	So I can prioritize maintenance activities

Spaces and Public Lighting		
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4.3 Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility

User	As a «type of user», I want «some goal» so that «some reason».
Stories ID	<i>Identify the costumer job(s) to which this user story relates.</i>	<i>Describe the intended goal that the user expects to be fulfilled.</i>	<i>Identify the reason(s) to which this user story relates.</i>
US12	As a Citizen Driver	I want to have credible information on available / crowded parking spaces in the city	So I can choose the right parking area and minimize the time looking for a parking space
US13	As a Head of the Municipal Police	I want to know the areas with high/low parking space requests	So I can allocate parking spaces between guests / residents more efficiently
US14	As a Head of the Municipal Police	I want to know the duration of each parking space occupation per area	So I can allocate parking spaces between guests / residents more efficiently
US15	As a Head of the Municipal Police	I want to know the allocation of parking fines per day/time	So I can allocate municipal officers patrol more efficiently
US16	As a Citizen Driver	I want to have a forecast when I will have a free space.	so i can decide to wait or find another parking
US17	As a Citizen Driver	I want to know the fares applied by the parking fines (per day/time)	so I can decide if I parking due to the nature of my appointment
US18	As a Citizen Driver	I want to get a parking recommendation (e.g. cheaper, closer) depending on a specific location	So i can decide the parking according to my specification
US19	As a Citizen Driver	i want to reserve a parking space	So I don't need to waste time looking for a parking space.
US20	As a Policy Maker	I want to have parking spaces available for people with reduced mobility	So i can provide a better service to people with reduced mobility by always parking where they want
US21	As a Policy Maker	I want to have parking spaces for different types of vehicles (e.g. cars, motorcycles)	So i can offer service to different types of user and optimize my parking spaces
US22	As a Citizen Driver	I want to define my personal parameters (e.g. reduced mobility, type of vehicle)	So i can access the park depending on my situation and benefit from quick and fair access

US23	As a Policy Maker	I want to know the areas with high/low parking space requests per time of day	So I can optimise fare prices and maximise Municipality revenue
US24	As a Policy Maker	Adapt the parking according to the type of demand, for example 1 space for a vehicle with reduced mobility = 1 car space + 1 motorcycle place = 4 motorcycle spaces	Optimize parking space according to demand
US25	As a Policy Maker	Attracting new customers to parking and motivating current customers by offering more advantageous prices e.g. discount at times when the parking has low space occupation and discounts if they reach x parking per month	Increase the satisfaction and adherence of new customers
US26	As a Policy Maker	Proactive / smart maintenance depending on the pattern of incidents, feedback on the beginning of problems, estimated time established by the manufacturer and so on	So i can minimizing the cost of the maintenance, service and repair activities

4.4 Policies for Citizens and Business Services Optimization

User	As a «type of user», I want « <u>some goal</u> » so that « <u>some reason</u> ».
Stories ID	<i>Identify the costumer job(s) to which this user story relates.</i>	<i>Describe the intended goal that the user expects to be fulfilled.</i>	<i>Identify the reason(s) to which this user story relates.</i>
US27	Policy Officer	Systematising data from different institutional sources	I can compose complex scenarios to identify risk locations or dynamics
US28	Policy Officer	Measuring the main indicators of road accidents	I can monitor the phenomenon and the incidence of actions taken and increase the knowledge and awareness of internal and external stakeholders
US29	Policy Officer	Involving citizens in surveying and assessing the danger of city areas.	I can increase the perception of risk and the sharing of actions taken
US30	Citizen	Receiving information on the danger of city areas	I can increase my perception of risk and implement

			behaviour aimed at reducing the probability of an accident
US31	Citizen	Being involved in the hazard assessment of city areas	I can give my contribution by providing relevant information that is not available from institutional or sensor data
US32	Citizen	Being involved in the assessment of the hazard of city areas	I can give my opinion on the results and the actions to be taken
US33	City Officer	Evaluation of the potentialities offered by the improvement of interoperability with wider systems (e.g. Regional or INPS DBs) for the efficiency of resources and the development of evidence-based policies in relation to social services	Improved allocation and use of human resources and other assets related to the social services
US34	City Officer/Citizen	Analysis and re-engineering of the transversal work process of the registry offices dealing in particular with registry office changes (immigrations, changes of residence, changes in civil status, AIRE registrations, etc.)	Better management of citizens' requests and communication towards them; enhanced internal communication between registry offices; improved allocation and use of human resources and other assets related to the demographic services; improvement of citizens' satisfaction
US35	City Officer/Citizen	Improved planning and execution of the extraordinary maintenance interventions	Enhancement of the potentialities offered by the "SegnalaCI" platform, including a better management of citizens' suggestions and reports; improvement of the quality of the municipal services and of the livability of the City; increased transparency, trustworthiness and accountability
US36	City Officer	Visualize data (of suggestions and reports) from the citizens (sent through the SegnalaCI platform) via Interactive map/dashboard	So i can better analyze the data
US37	City Officer	Status of the citizens' feedback (reports and/or suggestions) that have	So I can organize better and optimize the maintenance

		been addressed by the Municipality.	
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4.5 Policies for Holistic Urban Mobility and Accessibility

User	As a «type of user», I want « <u>some goal</u> » so that « <u>some reason</u> ».
Stories	<i>Identify the costumer job(s) to which this user story relates.</i>	<i>Describe the intended goal that the user expects to be fulfilled.</i>	<i>Identify the reason(s) to which this user story relates.</i>
US70	Citizen	I want to reach from point A to point B in the city in the faster and most cost-effective way	To save time and money when commuting to work
US71	Citizen	I want to move from point A to point B at the best possible time, where parking will be available, and the environment conditions are as healthy as possible	To save time when parking and to protect my health
US72	Policy Maker	I want to fine-tune the frequency of bus routes in order to ensure that multi-modal transport network operates in the more environmentally friendly way	To boost the sustainability performance of our municipality and to contribute to the European Green Deal
US73	Policy Maker	I want to fine-tune the capacity of the parking spaces in order to increase city revenues and to become streamlined to the buses' itineraries	To ensure that our urban mobility policies are streamlined and effective for multi-model transport
US74	Elderly/Disabled Citizen	I want the mobility services of my municipality (parking services, buses) to respect my needs	To live an active life and as much independent as possible
US75	Policy Maker	I want to create inclusiveness zones to the areas of our transport services that are used the most by elderly & disabled citizens	To provide them with accessible services that improve their Quality of Life and increase their satisfaction

4.6 Energy Management and Optimization Policies

User	As a «type of user», I want « <u>some goal</u> » so that « <u>some reason</u> ».
Stories	<i>Identify the costumer job(s) to which this user story relates.</i>	<i>Describe the intended goal that the user expects to be fulfilled.</i>	<i>Identify the reason(s) to which this user story relates.</i>

US38	City agency officer/Energy	To identify and locate the PV systems installed in the city as well as to know their areas	To understand about the city energy production performance; be able to deduce installed capacity; and infer about the city's PV adoption curve through time.
US39	City agency/Building(s) owner(s) officer/Energy	To know about the city's potential PV energy production.	To be able to monitor PV energy production potential and draw scenarios elucidating about the achievement of city's defined goals and targets for 2030.
US40	City agency officer/Energy	To realize buildings roof insulation capacity (i.e. thermal insulation performance). Identifying problems and cause analysis	To understand and infer about energy performance of existing buildings; to assist on city's investment needs calculation; and (possibly) support definition of potential financial mechanisms.
US41	City agency officer/Energy	Analyse PV datasets from different data sources (e.g. orthophotomaps, satellite images, and others available)	So I can have a wider range of datasets and that can help me analyse the potential of renewables (PV).
US42	Building(s) owner(s) and citizens	To know the potential PV energy production of the building(s) owner(s) and citizens	So i can provide estimates about potential cost savings
US43	City agency/Building(s) owner/Real Estate market officer/Energy	To know how external variables (e.g. temperature, humidity, solar exposure) influence buildings energy performance (roof level).	To understand how energy consumption varies with meteorological variables through root cause analysis.
US44	City agency/Building(s) owner/Real Estate market officer/Energy	To know how the impacts of different energy related interventions performed in the buildings	To be able to quantify impacts of performed interventions and better plan future interventions (considering the weather/climate forecast models);
US45	City agency officer/Energy	To ensure that the city's building register is updated regarding the type of uses (e.g. residential, services, etc.) at building level.	To better understand city's energy performance and energy consumption by sector of activity and be able to infer about potential energy demand through time.
US46	City agency officer/Energy	To define priorities with regard to the priorities for energy related buildings interventions.	To better define potential local financial mechanisms and, ultimately, ensure that

			impacts are aligned with goals defined for the city.
US47	City officer	Estimate about investment needs regarding the city's built environment	So i can make decisions about budget planning
US48	City agency officer/Energy	To map air temperature variations throughout the city (e.g. thermography images for on a monthly basis).	To understand the city thermal performance, locate the main hot spots and infer the reasons through root cause analysis, as well as to elucidate about 'urban heat island' effects.
US49	City agency officer/Energy	To be aware (visual way) of different pollutant's concentrations in different areas of the city and be automatically informed when these exceed the defined air quality limit values.	To monitor the air quality throughout the city, identify hot spots and inform citizens when air quality limit values are exceeded.
US50	Citizen	To know about city's temperature variations and air quality.	To better plan the trip to a specific point in the city or place to exercise.
US51	City officer	Correlate the data of the networks of sensors installed in the city with other information source	So with more data i can a better understand the city thermal and air quality performance
US52	City agency officer/Energy	To realize the carbon capture and storage capacity of the city's green areas.	To understand the potential impact of the green areas created in the recent years as well as their influence for the carbon emissions balance.
US53	City agency officer/Energy	To assess the non-CO2 greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions in the city.	To provide the developed policies, plans with more accurate information, as well as to be able to better monitor defined goal related to GHG inventory.

4.7 Policies for Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance

User	As a «type of user», I want « <u>some goal</u> » so that « <u>some reason</u> ».
Stories	<i>Identify the customer job(s) to which this user story relates.</i>	<i>Describe the intended goal that the user expects to be fulfilled.</i>	<i>Identify the reason(s) to which this user story relates.</i>
US54	WSSO executive	I want to know the amount of water lost due to pipe bursts or leakages	To ensure sufficient operational pressure in the pipes so that quality services can be provided

US55	Water Supply Manager for the Neighbourhood	I want to know the geographical distribution of leakages/illegal connections	So that I can stop them and to plan prevention activities
US56	Resident	I want good constant pressure, quality, and affordability of the water.	To have a good quality of life
US57	WSSO Engineer	I want to predict the status of the water supply (water level, pressure, etc)	To optimize and better plan my work
US58	WSSO Engineer	I want to know the error patterns at each control point.	To better analyse pipe performance
US59	WSSO public relations manager	I want adopt a more advanced maintenance strategy/policy	So I can maximise efficiency of maintenance activity reducing maintenance cost and service interruption.
US60	Burgas Municipality	As the owner of the water supply and sewerage networks, the municipality wants the cost of maintenance to be kept as low possible	Because this affects the price of water and allows for the social peace to be kept
US61	WSSO Engineer	I want to assess our technological capacities	So that realistic goals and development plans are made
US62	WSSO Technical Manager	I want to have planned repair works on the network	So that citizens are not so impacted by it
US63	Resident	I want to be informed about the planned repair work	So I can plan for water shortages
US64	WSSO Engineer	I want to undergo a digital transformation	So that we improve customer service delivery
US65	WSSO Engineer	I want to adopt smart water technologies and using AI to analyse large quantity of data	So that it frees up specialists time to work on something else and receive unbiased data results
US66	WSSO executive	I want to know the occurrence of incidents by location	I can manage the company better
US67	WSSO analyst	Report the difference in water (loss) before and after pipe replacement	So I can analyse the performance of the pipes
US68	WSSO analyst	Identify and prioritize the areas that suffer the greatest impacts of pipe repairing or replacing	To optimize the network

US69	WSSO executive	I want to know the costs of repair projects and accidents	Prioritize tasks that will bring the largest benefits and at the same time reduce maintenance costs
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5 Conclusions

The purpose of the Task 2.1 Reference Scenarios and Use Cases is to collect and analyse requirements regarding safe, secure, and citizen-centred AI in public policy development environments and the focus of this document is the collection of User Stories. These user stories bring together the issues, how to resolve them, and the reasons why they want to resolve the issues.

This document gathers information about the pilots, their use cases and user stories. This approach, based on the Value Proposition canvas, was divided in 3 Steps: update the pilot description, define use cases, and generate user stories.

This document D2.1 -Use case scenarios definition and design, provides an initial view on the Use Cases and User Stories provided by Ai4PublicPolicies Stakeholders, which will be used as the baseline for the technical WPs, that is, the user stories described in this document will be used as inputs in the technical WP, which will be the main outcome of the rest of Task 2.1. Currently, among the different 6 categories, we have a total of:

Figure 8: Total in the different categories

Appendices

Appendix 1 – Template User Stories

1 Pilot

Update the pilot description (pre-filled from the DoA)

Pilot	
Pilot Name	Pilot name
Summary	Short summary of the pilot (with a maximum of 280 char)
Description	Extended description of the pilot (text, images, etc.)
Motivation	Drivers and motivation for the pilot
	Place(s)
Place Name	Name of the place where the pilot will take place
Place Location	Place location: Country, County, City, Address, GPS – to the level of detail that can be shared
Characterisation	Characterisation of the present (as-is) state of the place. Examples: Existing Products, Processes, Sensors involved, etc.
Entity Name	Name of the local contact organisation
Logo	Logo (image + weblink) of the local contact organisation
Role	Role of the local contact organisation
Address	Address of the local contact organisation
Website	Website of the local contact organisation
Contact(s)	Name and email of the contact person(s)
Entity Type	Type of organisation: Higher or secondary education establishment; International Organisation; Non-governmental organization; Private for-profit organisation; Public organisation; Research organisation; Small or medium-size enterprise; Other.

2 Use Cases

Definition of the Use Cases for the described pilot (one table per Use Case).

2.1 Use Case #1

Use Case #1	
Use Case Name	Name of the Use Case
Summary	Short summary (with a maximum of 280 char) of the Use Case
Description	Extended description of the Use Case (text, images, etc.)
Value Proposition(s)	Bullet list with value proposition(s) of the Use Case:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ «Value Proposition #1 in the form ["Verb"] "direct object"» ▪ «Value Proposition #2 in the form ["Verb"] "direct object"» ▪ «Value Proposition #3 in the form ["Verb"] "direct object"» ▪ ... <p>Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ [Increase] Yield ▪ [Reduce] Pesticide Use ▪ [Improve] Water Quality ▪ [Reduce] Scrap parts
Documentation	Assorted documentation related to the Use Case
Image(s)	Photo gallery of the Use Case
Website	The website of the Use Case
Keywords	Set of keywords/tags that characterise the Use Case

3 User Stories

User Stories are short, simple descriptions of a feature told from the perspective of the person who desires the new capability, usually a user or customer of the system.

User Stories	As a «type of user», I want «some goal» so that «some reason».	Related UCs
	<i>Identify the costumer job(s) to which this user story relates.</i>	<i>Describe the intended goal that the user expects to be fulfilled.</i>	<i>Identify the reason(s) to which this user story relates.</i>	<i>Identify the Use Cases the User Story refers to</i>
User Story #1	« type of user »	« some goal »	« some reason »	« Use case # »
User Story #2	« type of user »	« some goal »	« some reason »	« Use case # »
User Story #3	« type of user »	« some goal »	« some reason »	« Use case # »
User Story #4	« type of user »	« some goal »	« some reason »	« Use case # »
User Story #5	« type of user »	« some goal »	« some reason »	« Use case # »
User Story #N	« type of user »	« some goal »	« some reason »	« Use case # »

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Appendix 2 – Complete List of Use Case

Use Case	Pilot	Use Cases Name	Summary	Description	Value Proposition(s)
UC01	Athens	Maintenance policies optimization	This use case will develop and validate policies for the optimal allocation of maintenance resources (e.g., workers, vehicles, materials), as well as for scheduling of different maintenance activities in the city.	This use case will develop and validate policies for the optimal allocation of maintenance resources (e.g., workers, vehicles, materials), as well as for scheduling of different activities in the city. The production of policies will take into account different parameters such as the type of infrastructure, the time needed for repair, the frequency of maintenance problems of specific types and in specific locations, possible bottleneck, as well as citizens' feedback on their satisfaction from the maintenance process and outcomes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce time in resolving reported incidents Reduce the average cost per incident for the city Increase citizen satisfaction from the infrastructure maintenance activities.
UC02	Athens	Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development	This use case will be based on the execution of AI analytics over transport data (notably parking information) as a means of providing citizens with prediction about parking availability in the different areas of the city, as well as on providing to the city a tool for optimal use of city-parking resources.	This use case will be based on the execution of AI analytics over transport data (notably parking information) as a means of providing citizens with prediction about parking availability in the different areas of the city. Taking into account historical data about parking spaces availability, fines imposed, fares paid and more, the AI4PublicPolicy tools will be used to recommend to citizens optimal tactics for finding parking spaces (e.g., locations with high-availability), as well as for optimizing their parking payments (i.e. fares during specific times of day and for specific locations). Citizens' feedback will be solicited in order to fine-tune the data-driven policies and the related recommendations. Likewise, the VPME will be used to identify policies for the creation/allocation of parking spaces for the citizens (i.e. identifying areas where there is sufficient availability of spaces and other locations where more parking zones are needed to be created).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased citizen satisfaction from the smart parking activities Increased revenue from parking Improved average parking availability Improved "fill rate" and occupancy for the parking positions.
UC03	Athens	Economic/Revenue Policies Modelling	This third use case will expand the previous two use cases with information about the city's revenues	-	-

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D2.1 – Use Case Scenarios Definition and Design

Use Case	Pilot	Use Cases Name	Summary	Description	Value Proposition(s)
			from the parking and the maintenance planning. In particular, the policy models of the previous use cases will be augmented with fiscal/monetary parameters in order to identify policies that maximize the city's revenues from the parking service, while minimizing the cost of the maintenance, service and repair activities.		
UC06	Genoa	Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people	This use case will execute ML/DL techniques to determine the danger index of city areas for the various vulnerable categories (pedestrians, cyclists, motorcyclists) in relation to possible causes (time, weather, environment, morphology, traffic, ...) in order to provide information and predictive analysis to decide and justify actions and interventions functional to reduce road accidents against vulnerable subjects.	The Interministerial Committee for Economic Planning and Sustainable Development (CIPESS) approved the National Road Safety Plan (NSSP) 2030 on 14 April 2022. The new National Road Safety Plan adopts the "Safe System" approach proposed by the European Commission and the UN 2030 Agenda, which aims to reduce the number of road fatalities and serious injuries by 50% by 2030 compared to 2019 and to zero by 2050. A key innovation of the UNDP 2030 is the definition of specific strategies for risk categories with targeted actions for each of them. The categories considered to be at greatest risk are: children and adolescents, young drivers, the over-65s, cyclists, pedestrians and users of powered two-wheelers. We are still waiting for the text to be made public. This will be followed by the adoption of individual implementation programmes that will define the details of the targeted interventions. In order to achieve the objectives of reducing road accidents and injuries it is necessary to intervene on the phenomenon with an analytical and dynamic approach. In the city of Genoa the traditional road safety interventions are undertaken by the decision makers, using the expertise of the technical bodies in charge, which refer to statistical elaborations that start from the data of accident events processed in an empirical way and not connected with other context elements that could increase the correct understanding of the events. It is therefore desirable to use an artificial intelligence tool that can provide useful information to be able to make decisions also on the basis of predictive elements to support decision-making policies. Artificial intelligence can in fact analyse and compose complex scenarios, which are impossible for human intelligence to process, and offer useful modelling to identify locations or risk dynamics. The improvement of the context	Evaluating the danger index of city areas in relation to possible causes. Extracting information and predictive analysis to decide and justify actions and interventions for reducing road accidents against vulnerable subjects.

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Use Case	Pilot	Use Cases Name	Summary	Description	Value Proposition(s)
				<p>analysis will be made possible by the assumption of additional data to those currently available and processed by the Local Police, with the implementation of additional data provided by the different structures operating in the field of road safety and that will systemise such data in the context of the local partnership. This will allow the construction of scenarios through the elaboration of artificial intelligence that will make available the potential derived from the large amount of data put into system. Through this information, the public administrator will have an advantage in evaluating the decisions to be implemented. A system designed in this way can allow moments of virtual involvement of citizens on the problem analysed, on the perception of the risk and on the sharing of the policies undertaken. The use of artificial intelligence will allow the processing of a complex amount of data, with analyses that man would do with enormous effort or would never be able to do. The optimisation of the processing times and the articulation of different sources of context, will be able to increase the knowledge of the phenomenon of road accidents in a sensitive way. It will be necessary to build a model that determines the danger index of the city areas for the various vulnerable categories (pedestrians, cyclists, motorcyclists) in relation to possible causes (time, weather, environment, morphology, traffic, ...) this will make it possible to provide information and predictive analysis to decide and justify, for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Inspections -Maintenance interventions -Speed limit reduction -Installation of remote speed control devices -Traffic modifications -Road closures at certain times or weather conditions/forecasts 	
UC07	Genoa	Optimizing the Allocation and Use of Resources for Social and Demographic Services also via fostering the interoperability between	This use case will execute ML/DL techniques over data about the citizens' requests for services and their handling workflows, towards identify optimal allocation of human resources and other assets (e.g., machines, equipment, software/hardware), in particular as regards two offices: social services	Within the framework of this use case, the intention is to identify optimal allocation of human resources and other assets (e.g., machines, equipment, software/hardware) related to the social and demographic services office and to evaluate the opportunities of interoperability with wider systems (e.g. Regional or INPS DBs), for the efficiency of resources and the development of evidence-based policies. It appears essential to be able to implement a process aimed at consolidating the existing system, also in relation	Optimizing the Allocation and Use of Resources for Social and Demographic/Registry Services, improvement of services to citizens and analysis towards the

D2.1 – Use Case Scenarios Definition and Design

Use Case	Pilot	Use Cases Name	Summary	Description	Value Proposition(s)
		information systems	office and demographic services office. As for the social services, in this direction it is key to evaluate how to improve the interoperability with wider systems (e.g. Regional or INPS DBs), for the efficiency of resources and the development of evidence-based policies. As for the demographic/registry services, efforts will be directed especially to the analysis and re-engineering of the transversal work process dealing in particular with registry office changes.	to interoperability with broader systems. This analysis, in particular as regards the social services office, could also be preparatory to the possible subsequent development of the following actions: 1. Analysis, design and possible implementation of a product that facilitates the interoperability of other systems, both within and outside the Public Administration, with the Social Policies information system; 2. Design of a data repository, with a good level of alignment/update of the developed data batteries, connecting with tools used by the Administration; 3. Construction of strategic reading models of the collected data, with a specific territorialisation and the possibility of longitudinal reading; 4. Return of useful information to the public decision-maker, through several options of proposals for "intelligent" analysis of the collected data. The outcome of the toolkit will be a set of data-driven recommendations and rules about how to best allocate and use resources for social and demographic services and enhance interoperability between information systems in order to make optimal use of resources, minimize service times and increase citizens' satisfaction. As for the demographic/registry services, the focus will be on the analysis and re-engineering of the transversal work process of the registry offices that deal in particular with registry office changes (immigrations, changes of residence, changes in civil status, AIRE registrations, etc.) with the aim of channelling citizens' requests, also by simplifying access to the portal, improving the ability to respond to citizens and internal communication between registry offices, including the multi-purpose desk. These are online practices. There is also a communication initiative towards citizens.	improvement of interoperability
UC08	Genoa	More effective extraordinary maintenance interventions by enhancing the "SegnalaCI" Citizens' Suggestions/Repo	This use case will improve the planning and deployment of extraordinary maintenance interventions also by an enhanced exploitation of the functionalities offered by the SegnalaCI platform. It allows to visualize data about citizens' suggestions and reports sent through the SegnalaCI platform	Through the SegnalaCI platform, citizens can make suggestions and reports to the Municipality of Genoa on a map (OpenStreetMap) in order to improve the quality of the services offered by the Administration itself and to improve the livability of the City, as well as to execute useful effective extraordinary maintenance interventions. In order to carry out the reporting activity and then use the SegnalaCI platform it is necessary to authenticate through Spid (public digital identity system) or register for the first time and thus	Improvement of the planning and execution of the extraordinary maintenance interventions, as well as the outcomes and value of SegnalaCI Platform

D2.1 – Use Case Scenarios Definition and Design

Use Case	Pilot	Use Cases Name	Summary	Description	Value Proposition(s)
		rts and Policies Visualizations	and about the workflows for handling them in an interactive map/dashboard. Information about the type, location, handling times, citizen demographics etc. associated with each request will be displayed and provided to both policy makers (inside the municipality) and citizens. The dashboard will be used to increase the transparency, trustworthiness and accountability of the policy development process.	obtain username and password, with which it will then be possible to make subsequent accesses. It is also possible to use the application via smartphone or tablet. Citizens can provide proposals, suggestions and reports on the map. In particular, suggestion means any proposal or communication, even of appreciation, by the citizen aimed at improving the quality of the services offered, whilst reporting means communication by the citizen regarding critical situations and / or malfunctions (eg signs, public lighting, holes in the streets, etc ...). The "report" is taken over by the municipal operators, who will forward to the responsible persons responsible for the matter within 48 hours, on weekdays. The answer will be provided on average within 15 days. With the official response from the institution, the report is closed. If the requested or suggested intervention has been deemed useful, necessary, and economically sustainable by the service manager, it will be included in the Administration's programs, on the basis of the priorities decided by the body itself and according to the methods and times defined independently by the Office. This service has been in use since November 20020, when 200 volunteer citizens began to test the platform in advance. Since January 4, 2021, the platform has been open to all citizens. Since the opening, 2193 new citizens have registered. In recent weeks, the number of registered citizens has increased and also the number of reports forwarded to the Administration through ReportCi: the greatest number of reports concerns the facility, the environment, PL and mobility This use case will visualize data about this citizens' suggestions and reports and about the workflows for handling them, with a focus on extraordinary maintenance interventions (on flowerbed borders, city squares and pedestrian areas, pavements and stairways, street mowing, etc.) and the overall Maintenance Plan of the Municipality of Genoa, in an interactive map/dashboard. Information about the type, location, handling times, citizen demographics etc. associated with each suggestion and report will be displayed and provided to both policy makers (inside the municipality) and citizens. The dashboard will be used to increase the transparency, trustworthiness and accountability of the policy development process. SegnalaCI's functionalities might also be enriched to cover the citizens' feedback on how their	

D2.1 – Use Case Scenarios Definition and Design

Use Case	Pilot	Use Cases Name	Summary	Description	Value Proposition(s)
				reports and/or suggestions have been addressed by the Municipality. The VPME will provide the means for using the AI policy development tools of the above use cases at a strategic level. Hence, they will facilitate not only the creation/formulation of policies, but also their reprogramming and reconfiguration as well. All policy development use cases will engage both citizens and policy makers from CDG. Furthermore, as part of the pilot, the project will also study and implement the required organizational transformation activities.	
UC09	Lisbon	Renewables (PV) potential and performance analysis	This use case will identify existing assets and assess the potential renewables (PV) production.	This use case aims to identify the PV systems existing in the city as well as create methods to assess and determine accurately their production potential. In a first stage, the goal will be to identify and locate the PV systems installed in the city in order to understand about the current energy production performance in the city and infer about the city's PV adoption curve through time. These analytics should be made by using different available datasets, including orthophotomaps, satellite images, and others available, as well as those provided by existing platforms (e.g. Solis platform). In a second stage, this use case should provide users with the ability to monitor PV energy production potential, ideally by defining time series and forecast scenarios (e.g. on "day-ahead"; "month ahead"; "quarter ahead", etc.). This aims to enable the definition of scenarios elucidating about the achievement of city's defined goals and targets for 2030, as well as to inform building(s) owner(s) and citizens about the potential PV production of their buildings, as well as to provide with estimates about potential cost savings.	tbd
UC10	Lisbon	Buildings Energy Performance Analysis	This use case will identify problems in the buildings' energy performance and will perform root cause analysis.	This use case aims to provide user with the ability to better understand about the buildings energy performance. Considering the data availability, the focus should be at defining buildings insulation capacity at the roof level (i.e. thermal insulation performance) and to assess how external variables (e.g. temperature, humidity, solar exposure) influence buildings energy performance/consumption. The goals are manifold and include: understanding about energy performance of existing buildings, that will drive the analysis on city's investment needs, and (possibly) support definition of potential financial mechanisms (UC#3); to understand how energy consumption varies with	tbd

D2.1 – Use Case Scenarios Definition and Design

Use Case	Pilot	Use Cases Name	Summary	Description	Value Proposition(s)
				meteorological variables through root cause analysis; and to better understand about the impacts of different energy related interventions performed in the buildings (monitoring analysis), which can be used to better plan future interventions.	
UC11	Lisbon	Budget Planning for Energy Usage and Buildings Renovation	This use cases will focus on policy making decisions on budget planning and effective use of budget and public resources towards buildings renovation and energy usage. For instance, policies for the definition of specific financial supporting mechanisms or retrofit schemes will be recommended.	This use case is partially a consequence of UC#2. Its goal is to provide the user with the ability to better estimate about investment needs regarding the city's built environment and support the definition of priorities for potential local financial mechanisms aimed at increasing buildings energy efficiency and city's overall energy performance.	tbd
UC12	Lisbon	City's thermal and air quality performance	This use cases will focus on providing visual and interactive support to understand temperature and air quality variations throughout the city.	This use case aims to take advantage from the networks of sensors installed in the city that, together with other information source, should provide the user with the ability to map air temperature and air quality variations throughout the city. The goal is to understand the city thermal and air quality performance, locate the main hot spots and infer the reasons through root cause analysis, as well as to elucidate about 'urban heat island' effects and the locations exposed to higher concentrations of pollutants. In addition, the provision of this information to citizens is also intended, allowing for instance better planning trips to a specific point in the city according to current temperatures and/or pollutants exposure levels.	tbd
UC13	Lisbon	City's greenhouse gases emissions	This use cases will focus on assessing city's carbon capture and storage capacity and provide estimates on non-CO2 greenhouse gases.	This use case aims to realize the carbon capture and storage capacity of the city's green and river areas, in order to support and better determine carbon balance assessments and progression through time. By using data past and current time series, this should provide the user with the ability to understand the potential impact of the green areas created in the recent years as well as their influence for the carbon emissions balance. Focusing on the non-CO2 greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions, the goal is to determine emission and concentration levels, supporting the monitoring of development policies with more accurate information, as well as to be able to better monitor defined goal related to GHG inventory.	tbd

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Use Case	Pilot	Use Cases Name	Summary	Description	Value Proposition(s)
UC04	Burgas	Smart Water Management System - Pobeda Residential Neighbourhood	This use case will measure the water losses and identify those that are due to unauthorized consumption. Subsequently, it will develop data-driven policies for the prevention of damages and losses.	This use case will develop data-driven policies for the maintenance of the water management infrastructure by monitoring and measuring the water inflow and using AI to analyse and process the data. The Pilot smart pipe will be installed in a zone called District Metered Area (DMA) and it has 1131 water supply connections and approximately 8200 residents. The neighbourhood was chosen because it has a predominantly Roma population and historically low rates of bill collection, assumed to be due to the low income and illegal water connections. This directly affects the operational quality of the network. Beside the various problems that could be managed, that the pilot should take into consideration, the most important is to identify directly or indirectly which losses are due to leakages and unauthorized consumption. The historically measured data will be utilized to train the AI that will later provide information on the amount and type of water losses. The AI algorithms will try to find the most likely status of the water supply network after assigning a certain degree of uncertainty to the existing data and perform a continuous calibration on the network. This will allow an analysis of the structure of the errors (difference between the measurements and predictions) at each control point, and it will allow information to be extracted from the error patterns.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ [Reduce] Physical Water Losses ▪ [Reduce] Commercial Water Losses ▪ [Improve] Water Quality ▪ [Control] Water Tariff Increases ▪ [Optimize] Capital Investment ▪ [Reduce] Operating Costs ▪ [Benefit] Consumers ▪ [Support] Sustainable Development Goals ▪ [Deliver] Better Service
UC05	Burgas	Condition-based Monitoring and LCA for Maintenance and Repair Policies	This use case will develop data-driven policies for the maintenance of mains water infrastructure.	This use case will develop data-driven policies for the maintenance of mains water infrastructure by monitoring and measuring the water inflow and the corresponding pressure on a continual basis for the primary water distribution network on Industrialna street, which is a steel pipe with diameter of 530 millimetres and length of 1450 metres. The chosen location and pipe is known for a lot of accidents (i.e. pipe bursts) in the past and the pipe should be replaced with a new one. This will provide the AI with important, valuable and irreplaceable information of historical data, measurements before and after the new pipe installation. The measured data will be utilized to train the AI that will later evaluate the condition of the pipe and after replacement the difference in water losses will be measured. The process will provide us with information that can later be upscaled to wider proportions of the net. This will help to identify, prioritize and target the areas that will bring the largest benefits and at the same time reduce maintenance costs because of strategically placed efforts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪[Prioritize] Pipe Replacement ▪[Optimize] Distribution Network Sectorization ▪[Reduce] Physical Water Losses ▪[Reduce] Commercial Water Losses ▪[Improve] Water Quality ▪[Control] Water Tariff Increases ▪[Optimize] Capital Investment ▪[Reduce] Operating Costs ▪[Benefit] Consumers ▪[Support] Sustainable

D2.1 – Use Case Scenarios Definition and Design

Use Case	Pilot	Use Cases Name	Summary	Description	Value Proposition(s)
				(e.g. installing fewer sensors and repairing or replacing the pipes with the biggest impact first).	Development Goals •[Deliver] Better Service
UC14	Nicosia	Optimal Urban mobility policies for citizens	This use case will extract and provide to citizens data-driven optimal policies about their mobility in the cities.	Leveraging data about bus routes & occupancy, parking usage, and citizens' preferences, this use case will create optimal mobility policies for buses and parking spaces, notably policies that reduce travel times and travel costs in multi-modal transport scenarios combining bus, car, and walking transport modalities. The proposed policies will provide recommendations about the frequency of buses at certain times of the day/week and the planning of parking spaces to ensure availability for the citizens. One of the main innovations of the use case will be the use of machine learning and XAI to provide passenger centered recommendations of optimal mobility options, which is typically lacking in smart mobility solutions. Citizens' feedback will be received and integrated using surveys and co-creation sessions.	Evidence-based policies that enable citizens to move faster, save time, cost and improve the city's environmental performance.
UC15	Nicosia	Optimal Urban mobility policies for the Municipality	This use case will recommend/introduce policies that optimize city's goals such as sustainability and transport operational cost, while taking into account citizens' feedback and satisfaction.	This use case will produce urban mobility policies that optimize resources (e.g., bus itineraries, parking spaces revenue) and environmental performance (e.g., CO2 emissions, fuel consumption). In this direction, it will leverage CO2/environmental measurements from the Smart City platform, information about bus routes and travel times, as well as estimates about fuel consumption and the environmental impact of different modes of mobility. Citizens' feedback will be received and integrated using surveys and co-creation sessions.	-Improved environmental performance for the city; -Improved Resources management and optimization
UC16	Nicosia	Accessible urban mobility policies	This use cases will target people with disabilities towards improving their accessibility to the mobility services of the municipality and their overall inclusion in the city's transport ecosystem.	This use case will create inclusiveness zones around bus stops and parking spaces for disabled people. These zones will aim at optimizing the overall health environment (e.g., CO2, noise) for the citizens, while offering them the best possible quality of service. Leveraging historical data about bus stops and parking spaces, the municipality will specify policies for improving the health environment (e.g., noise reduction policies/fines on local shops, CO2 reduction policies), as well as policies for improving the offered services (e.g., deployment of inclusiveness agent) and the surrounding environment (e.g., tree planting).	-Improved accessibility, inclusiveness and sustainability of urban mobility services; -Higher satisfaction for elderly, disabled or handicapped citizens

Appendix 3 – Complete List of User Stories

User Story	Pilot	As a «type of user», I want «some goal» so that «some reason».	Related UCs	Use Case Name	Category
US01	Athens	As a Head of Urban Planning Dpt	I want to see a prediction/forecast of the completion time for each type of incident	so that I can provide a data driven feedback to citizens and the head of operations regarding the completion time	UC01	Maintenance optimization policies	Policies Infrastructures Maintenance Repair for and
US02	Athens	As a Head of Urban Planning Dpt	I want to have a prediction of the incidents frequency per season of the year	in order to be able to plan the seasonal personnel according to forecasted needs	UC01	Maintenance optimization policies	Policies Infrastructures Maintenance Repair for and
US03	Athens	As a Head of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management Dpt	i want to be able to set a route of incident fixes locations based on shortest path principle	so that i can optimize the personnel moving and vehicle costs and minimise the resolution time.	UC01	Maintenance optimization policies	Policies Infrastructures Maintenance Repair for and
US04	Athens	As a Head of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management Dpt	I want to receive feedback from citizens about maintenance issues handling	So I can improve the issue response time and quality	UC01	Maintenance optimization policies	Policies Infrastructures Maintenance Repair for and
US05	Athens	As a City Employee (in the Dpt of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management/Urban Planning/Urban Green Spaces and Public Lighting	I want to have a prediction of incidents occurrence frequency	So I can plan equipment / materials purchases in optimal prices (economies of scale, etc.)	UC01	Maintenance optimization policies	Policies Infrastructures Maintenance Repair for and
US06	Athens	As a City Employee (in the Dpt of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management/Urban Planning/Urban Green Spaces and Public Lighting	I want to have an overview of the predicted maintenance needs in city assets (e.g. roads, lightning, pedestrian etc)	So I can schedule activities more efficiently	UC01	Maintenance optimization policies	Policies Infrastructures Maintenance Repair for and
US07	Athens	As a Head of Dpt of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management/Urban Planning/Urban Green	I want to have an output report on estimated predictions for the timeline, human resources and cost of maintenance of the city	So I can provide maintenance services proactively and increase QoS life in the city	UC01	Maintenance optimization policies	Policies Infrastructures Maintenance Repair for and

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User Story	Pilot	As a «type of user», I want «some goal» so that «some reason».	Related UCs	Use Case Name	Category
		Spaces and Public Lighting					
US08	Athens	As a citizen	I want to be informed of the outcome of my complaint / report	So I can be sure my complaint has been addressed	UC01	Maintenance optimization policies	Policies for Infrastructures Maintenance and Repair
US09	Athens	As a City Worker	I want to have a schedule of the foreseen maintenance and other repairing issues	So I can estimate and manage my weekly/monthly workload	UC01	Maintenance optimization policies	Policies for Infrastructures Maintenance and Repair
US10	Athens	As a Head of Dpt of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management/Urban Planning/Urban Green Spaces and Public Lighting	I want to have a real-time idea of the teams (e.g. workers, vehicles) that are on the field.	So i can optimal scheduling of maintenance. E.g if there is something to do near the team on the field, the scheduling could be readjusted	UC01	Maintenance optimization policies	Policies for Infrastructures Maintenance and Repair
US11	Athens	As a Head of Dpt of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management/Urban Planning/Urban Green Spaces and Public Lighting	Classify the incident by its maintenance urgency	So I can prioritize maintenance activities	UC01	Maintenance optimization policies	Policies for Infrastructures Maintenance and Repair
US12	Athens	As a Citizen Driver	I want to have credible information on available / crowded parking spaces in the city	So I can choose the right parking area and minimize the time looking for a parking space	UC02	Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development	Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility
US13	Athens	As a Head of the Municipal Police	I want to know the areas with high/low parking space requests	So I can allocate parking spaces between guests / residents more efficiently	UC02	Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development	Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility
US14	Athens	As a Head of the Municipal Police	I want to know the duration of each parking space occupation per area	So I can allocate parking spaces between guests / residents more efficiently	UC02	Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development	Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility

D2.1 – Use Case Scenarios Definition and Design

User Story	Pilot	As a «type of user», I want «some goal» so that «some reason».	Related UCs	Use Case Name	Category
US15	Athens	As a Head of the Municipal Police	I want to know the allocation of parking fines per day/time	So I can allocate municipal officers patrol more efficiently	UC02	Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development	Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility
US16	Athens	As a Citizen Driver	I want to have a forecast when I will have a free space.	so i can decide to wait or find another parking	UC02	Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development	Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility
US17	Athens	As a Citizen Driver	I want to know the fares applied by the parking fines (per day/time)	so I can decide if I parking due to the nature of my appointment	UC02	Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development	Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility
US18	Athens	As a Citizen Driver	I want to get a parking recommendation (e.g. cheaper, closer) depending on a specific location	So i can decide the parking according to my specification	UC02	Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development	Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility
US19	Athens	As a Citizen Driver	i want to reserve a parking space	So I don't need to waste time looking for a parking space.	UC02	Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development	Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility
US20	Athens	As a Policy Maker	I want to have parking spaces available for people with reduced mobility	So i can provide a better service to people with reduced mobility by always parking where they want	UC02	Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development	Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility
US21	Athens	As a Policy Maker	I want to have parking spaces for different types of vehicles (e.g. cars, motorcycles)	So i can offer service to different types of user and optimize my parking spaces	UC02	Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development	Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility
US22	Athens	As a Citizen Driver	I want to define my personal parameters (e.g. reduced mobility, type of vehicle)	So i can access the park depending on my situation and benefit from quick and fair access	UC02	Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development	Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility
US23	Athens	As a Policy Maker	I want to know the areas with high/low parking space requests per time of day	So I can optimise fare prices and maximise Municipality revenue	UC03	Economic/Revenue Policies Modelling	Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility

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User Story	Pilot	As a «type of user», I want «some goal» so that «some reason».	Related UCs	Use Case Name	Category
US24	Athens	As a Policy Maker	Adapt the parking according to the type of demand, for example 1 space for a vehicle with reduced mobility = 1 car space + 1 motorcycle place = 4 motorcycle spaces	Optimize parking space according to demand	UC03	Economic/Revenue Policies Modelling	Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility
US25	Athens	As a Policy Maker	Attracting new customers to parking and motivating current customers by offering more advantageous prices e.g. discount at times when the parking has low space occupation and discounts if they reach x parking per month	Increase the satisfaction and adherence of new customers	UC03	Economic/Revenue Policies Modelling	Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility
US26	Athens	As a Policy Maker	Proactive / smart maintenance depending on the pattern of incidents, feedback on the beginning of problems, estimated time established by the manufacturer and so on	So i can minimizing the cost of the maintenance, service and repair activities	UC03	Economic/Revenue Policies Modelling	Policies for Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility
US27	Genoa	Policy Officer	Systematising data from different institutional sources	I can compose complex scenarios to identify risk locations or dynamics	UC06	Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people	Policies for Citizens and Business Services Optimization
US28	Genoa	Policy Officer	Measuring the main indicators of road accidents	I can monitor the phenomenon and the incidence of actions taken and increase the knowledge and awareness of internal and external stakeholders	UC06	Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people	Policies for Citizens and Business Services Optimization
US29	Genoa	Policy Officer	Involving citizens in surveying and assessing the danger of city areas.	I can increase the perception of risk and the sharing of actions taken	UC06	Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people	Policies for Citizens and Business Services Optimization
US30	Genoa	Citizen	Receiving information on the danger of city areas	I can increase my perception of risk and implement behaviour	UC06	Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people	Policies for Citizens and Business Services Optimization

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User Story	Pilot	As a «type of user», I want «some goal» so that «some reason».	Related UCs	Use Case Name	Category
				aimed at reducing the probability of an accident			
US31	Genoa	Citizen	Being involved in the hazard assessment of city areas	I can give my contribution by providing relevant information that is not available from institutional or sensor data	UC06	Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people	Policies for Citizens and Business Services Optimization
US32	Genoa	Citizen	Being involved in the assessment of the hazard of city areas	I can give my opinion on the results and the actions to be taken	UC06	Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people	Policies for Citizens and Business Services Optimization
US33	Genoa	City Officer	Evaluation of the potentialities offered by the improvement of interoperability with wider systems (e.g. Regional or INPS DBs) for the efficiency of resources and the development of evidence-based policies in relation to social services	Improved allocation and use of human resources and other assets related to the social services	UC07	Optimizing the Allocation and Use of Resources for Social and Demographic Services also via fostering the interoperability between information systems	Policies for Citizens and Business Services Optimization
US34	Genoa	City Officer/Citizen	Analysis and re-engineering of the transversal work process of the registry offices dealing in particular with registry office changes (immigrations, changes of residence, changes in civil status, AIRE registrations, etc.)	Better management of citizens' requests and communication towards them; enhanced internal communication between registry offices; improved allocation and use of human resources and other assets related to the demographic services; improvement of citizens' satisfaction	UC07	Optimizing the Allocation and Use of Resources for Social and Demographic Services also via fostering the interoperability between information systems	Policies for Citizens and Business Services Optimization
US35	Genoa	City Officer/Citizen	Improved planning and execution of the extraordinary maintenance interventions	Enhancement of the potentialities offered by the "SegnalaCI" platform, including a better management of citizens' suggestions and reports; improvement of the quality of the municipal services and of the livability of the City; increased	UC08	More effective extraordinary maintenance interventions by enhancing the "SegnalaCI" Citizens' Suggestions/Reports and Policies Visualizations	Policies for Citizens and Business Services Optimization

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User Story	Pilot	As a «type of user», I want «some goal» so that «some reason».	Related UCs	Use Case Name	Category
				transparency, trustworthiness and accountability			
US36	Genoa	City Officer	Visualize data (of suggestions and reports) from the citizens (sent through the SegnalaCI platform) via Interactive map/dashboard	So i can better analyze the data	UC08	More effective extraordinary maintenance interventions by enhancing the “SegnalaCI” Citizens’ Suggestions/Reports and Policies Visualizations	Policies for Citizens and Business Services Optimization
US37	Genoa	City Officer	Status of the citizens’ feedback (reports and/or suggestions) that have been addressed by the Municipality.	So I can organize better and optimize the maintenance	UC08	More effective extraordinary maintenance interventions by enhanceing the “SegnalaCI” Citizens’ Suggestions/Reports and Policies Visualizations	Policies for Citizens and Business Services Optimization
US38	Lisbon	City officer/Energy agency	To identify and locate the PV systems installed in the city as well as to know their areas	To understand about the city energy production performance; be able to deduce installed capacity; and infer about the city’s PV adoption curve through time.	UC09	Renewables (PV) potential and performance analysis	Energy and Management Optimization Policies
US39	Lisbon	City officer/Energy agency/Building(s) owner(s)	To know about the city’s potential PV energy production.	To be able to monitor PV energy production potential and draw scenarios elucidating about the achievement of city’s defined goals and targets for 2030.	UC09	Renewables (PV) potential and performance analysis	Energy and Management Optimization Policies
US40	Lisbon	City officer/Energy agency	To realize buildings roof insulation capacity (i.e. thermal insulation performance). Identifying problems and cause analysis	To understand and infer about energy performance of existing buildings; to assist on city’s investment needs calculation; and (possibly) support definition of potential financial mechanisms.	UC09	Renewables (PV) potential and performance analysis	Energy and Management Optimization Policies

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User Story	Pilot	As a «type of user», I want «some goal» so that «some reason».	Related UCs	Use Case Name	Category
US41	Lisbon	City officer/Energy agency	Analyse PV datasets from different data sources (e.g. orthophotomaps, satellite images, and others available)	So I can have a wider range of datasets and that can help me analyse the potential of renewables (PV).	UC09	Renewables (PV) potential and performance analysis	Energy Management and Optimization Policies
US42	Lisbon	Building(s) owner(s) and citizens	To know the potential PV energy production of the building(s) owner(s) and citizens	So i can provide estimates about potential cost savings	UC09	Renewables (PV) potential and performance analysis	Energy Management and Optimization Policies
US43	Lisbon	City officer/Energy agency/Building(s) owner/Real Estate market	To know how external variables (e.g. temperature, humidity, solar exposure) influence buildings energy performance (roof level).	To understand how energy consumption varies with meteorological variables through root cause analysis.	UC10	Buildings Energy Performance Analysis	Energy Management and Optimization Policies
US44	Lisbon	City officer/Energy agency/Building(s) owner/Real Estate market	To know how the impacts of different energy related interventions performed in the buildings	To be able to quantify impacts of performed interventions and better plan future interventions (considering the weather/climate forecast models);	UC10	Buildings Energy Performance Analysis	Energy Management and Optimization Policies
US45	Lisbon	City officer/Energy agency	To ensure that the city's building register is updated regarding the type of uses (e.g. residential, services, etc.) at building level.	To better understand city's energy performance and energy consumption by sector of activity, and be able to infer about potential energy demand through time.	UC10 & UC11	Buildings Energy Performance Analysis & Budget Planning for Energy Usage and Buildings Renovation	Energy Management and Optimization Policies
US46	Lisbon	City officer/Energy agency	To define priorities with regard to the priorities for energy related buildings interventions.	To better define potential local financial mechanisms and, ultimately, ensure that impacts are aligned with goals defined for the city.	UC11	Budget Planning for Energy Usage and Buildings Renovation	Energy Management and Optimization Policies
US47	Lisbon	City officer?	Estimate about investment needs regarding the city's built environment	So i can make decisions about budget planning	UC11	Budget Planning for Energy Usage and Buildings Renovation	Energy Management and Optimization Policies
US48	Lisbon	City officer/Energy agency	To map air temperature variations throughout the city (e.g. thermography)	To understand the city thermal performance, locate the main hot spots and infer the reasons through root cause analysis, as	UC12	City's thermal and air quality performance	Energy Management and Optimization Policies

D2.1 – Use Case Scenarios Definition and Design

User Story	Pilot	As a «type of user», I want «some goal» so that «some reason».	Related UCs	Use Case Name	Category
			images for on a monthly basis).	well as to elucidate about 'urban heat island' effects.			
US49	Lisbon	City agency officer/Energy	To be aware (visual way) of different pollutant's concentrations in different areas of the city, and be automatically informed when these exceed the defined air quality limit values.	To monitor the air quality throughout the city, identify hot spots and inform citizens when air quality limit values are exceeded.	UC12	City's thermal and air quality performance	Energy Management and Optimization Policies
US50	Lisbon	Citizen	To know about city's temperature variations and air quality.	To better plan the trip to a specific point in the city or place to exercise.	UC12	City's thermal and air quality performance	Energy Management and Optimization Policies
US51	Lisbon	City officer	Correlate the data of the networks of sensors installed in the city with other information source	So with more data i can a better understand the city thermal and air quality performance	UC12	City's thermal and air quality performance	Energy Management and Optimization Policies
US52	Lisbon	City agency officer/Energy	To realize the carbon capture and storage capacity of the city's green areas.	To understand the potential impact of the green areas created in the recent years as well as their influence for the carbon emissions balance.	UC13	City's greenhouse gases emissions	Energy Management and Optimization Policies
US53	Lisbon	City agency officer/Energy	To assess the non-CO2 greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions in the city.	To provide the developed policies, plans with more accurate information, as well as to be able to better monitor defined goal related to GHG inventory.	UC13	City's greenhouse gases emissions	Energy Management and Optimization Policies
US54	Burgas	WSSO executive	I want to know the amount of water lost due to pipe bursts or leakages	to ensure sufficient operational pressure in the pipes so that quality services can be provided	UC04	Smart Water Management System - Pobeda Residential Neighbourhood	Policies for Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
US55	Burgas	Water Supply Manager for the neighbourhood	I want to know the geographical distribution of leakages/illegal connections	so that I can stop them and to plan prevention activities	UC04	Smart Water Management System - Pobeda Residential Neighbourhood	Policies for Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance

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User Story	Pilot	As a «type of user», I want «some goal» so that «some reason».	Related UCs	Use Case Name	Category
US56	Burgas	Resident	I want good constant pressure, quality, and affordability of the water.	to have a good quality of life	UC04	Smart Water Management System - Pobeda Residential Neighbourhood	Policies for Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
US57	Burgas	WSSO Engineer	I want to predict the status of the water supply (water level, pressure, etc)	To optimize and better plan my work	UC04	Smart Water Management System - Pobeda Residential Neighbourhood	Policies for Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
US58	Burgas	WSSO Engineer	I want to know the error patterns at each control point.	To better analyse pipe performance	UC04	Smart Water Management System - Pobeda Residential Neighborhood	Policies for Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
US59	Burgas	WSSO public relations manager	I want adopt a more advanced maintenance strategy/policy	So I can maximise efficiency of maintenance activity reducing maintenance cost and service interruption.	UC04	Smart Water Management System - Pobeda Residential Neighborhood	Policies for Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
US60	Burgas	Burgas Municipality	As the owner of the water supply and sewerage networks, the municipality wants the cost of maintenance to be kept as low possible	Because this affects the price of water and allows for the social peace to be kept	UC05	Condition-based Monitoring and LCA for Maintenance and Repair Policies	Policies for Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
US61	Burgas	WSSO Engineer	I want to assess our technological capacities	So that realistic goals and development plans are made	UC05	Condition-based Monitoring and LCA for Maintenance and Repair Policies	Policies for Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
US62	Burgas	WSSO Technical Manager	I want to have planned repair works on the network	So that citizens are not so impacted by it	UC05	Condition-based Monitoring and LCA for Maintenance and Repair Policies	Policies for Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
US63	Burgas	Resident	I want to be informed about the planned repair work	So I can plan for water shortages	UC05	Condition-based Monitoring and LCA for Maintenance and Repair Policies	Policies for Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
US64	Burgas	WSSO Engineer	I want to undergo a digital transformation	So that we improve customer service delivery	UC05	Condition-based Monitoring and LCA for Maintenance and Repair Policies	Policies for Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance

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User Story	Pilot	As a «type of user», I want «some goal» so that «some reason».	Related UCs	Use Case Name	Category
US65	Burgas	WSSO Engineer	I want to adopt smart water technologies and using AI to analyse large quantity of data	So that it frees up specialists time to work on something else and receive unbiased data results	UC05	Condition-based Monitoring and LCA for Maintenance and Repair Policies	Policies for Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
US66	Burgas	WSSO executive	I want to know the occurrence of incidents by location	I can manage the company better	UC05	Condition-based Monitoring and LCA for Maintenance and Repair Policies	Policies for Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
US67	Burgas	WSSO analyst	Report the difference in water (loss) before and after pipe replacement	So I can analyse the performance of the pipes	UC05	Condition-based Monitoring and LCA for Maintenance and Repair Policies	Policies for Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
US68	Burgas	WSSO analyst	Identify and prioritize the areas that suffer the greatest impacts of pipe repairing or replacing	To optimize the network	UC05	Condition-based Monitoring and LCA for Maintenance and Repair Policies	Policies for Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
US69	Burgas	WSSO executive	I want to know the costs of repair projects and accidents	Prioritize tasks that will bring the largest benefits and at the same time reduce maintenance costs	UC05	Condition-based Monitoring and LCA for Maintenance and Repair Policies	Policies for Data-driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance
US70	Nicosia	Citizen	I want to reach from point A to point B in the city in the faster and most cost-effective way	To save time and money when commuting to work	UC14	Optimal Urban mobility policies for citizens	Policies for Holistic Urban Mobility and Accessibility
US71	Nicosia	Citizen	I want to move from point A to point B at the best possible time, where parking will be available, and the environment conditions are as healthy as possible	To save time when parking and to protect my health	UC14	Optimal Urban mobility policies for citizens	Policies for Holistic Urban Mobility and Accessibility
US72	Nicosia	Policy Maker	I want to fine-tune the frequency of bus routes in order to ensure that multi-modal transport network operates in the more environmentally friendly way	To boost the sustainability performance of our municipality and to contribute to the European Green Deal	UC15	Optimal Urban mobility policies for the Municipality	Policies for Holistic Urban Mobility and Accessibility

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User Story	Pilot	As a «type of user», I want «some goal» so that «some reason».	Related UCs	Use Case Name	Category
US73	Nicosia	Policy Maker	I want to fine-tune the capacity of the parking spaces in order to increase city revenues and to become streamlined to the buses' itineraries	To ensure that our urban mobility policies are streamlined and effective for multi-model transport	UC15	Optimal Urban mobility policies for the Municipality	Policies for Holistic Urban Mobility and Accessibility
US74	Nicosia	Elderly/Disabled Citizen	I want the mobility services of my municipality (parking services, buses) to respect my needs	To live an active life and as much independent as possible	UC16	Accessible urban mobility policies	Policies for Holistic Urban Mobility and Accessibility
US75	Nicosia	Policy Maker	I want to create inclusiveness zones to the areas of our transport services that are used the most by elderly & disabled citizens	To provide them with accessible services that improve their Quality of Life and increase their satisfaction	UC16	Accessible urban mobility policies	Policies for Holistic Urban Mobility and Accessibility